
Controls for Integrated Solid Oxide Fuel Cell, Solar and Storage System to achieve Zero Net Energy in a Residential Nanogrid Final Report

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Executive Summary

This report continues our work on evaluating the potential role of solid oxide fuel cells (SOFCs) in achieving zero net energy (ZNE) in residential nanogrids, particularly within California's stringent energy standards and decarbonization goals. A residential nanogrid, for this work, refers to a building equipped with energy technologies capable of operating independently from the electrical grid.

Our prior optimization studies showed that the lowest-cost ZNE nanogrids include SOFCs powered by renewable hydrogen, operating alongside solar photovoltaics (PV) and battery energy storage (ESS). These systems rely on dynamic dispatch of SOFCs and ESS to achieve cost-optimal performance. Dynamic dispatch for nanogrid systems would typically be resolved using either an optimization based approach, or a heuristics/rules based approach. The optimization approach uses mathematical tools to continuously tune energy system operation in order to achieve a stated operational goal, such as lowest cost, ZNE, and/or lowest emissions. Heuristics/rules based approaches attempt to replicate optimal controls through the use of a combination of operational schedules and rules. This study aims to experimentally validate whether an SOFC-based ZNE system can operate as predicted and assess whether commercially available nanogrid controllers can replicate the optimal energy system operation.

During the project, equipment communication issues significantly delayed progress. The primary challenge was battery integration—the inverter did not accept commands from third-party control systems. These challenges were eventually overcome by replacing the inverter with a different model that allowed for communication.

This study also introduces a new economic analysis of SOFCs for ZNE nanogrids. Using updated UCI optimization models, we quantify the value of SOFC systems as a function of capacity and fuel cost. Additionally, we provide a first-of-its-kind comparison between SOFCs and proton exchange membrane fuel cells (PEMFCs) for residential applications. This analysis is critical, as the residential fuel cell market remains small, and manufacturers have yet to achieve economies of scale needed to lower costs.

This work assumes the availability of renewable hydrogen. Since California's ZNE target effectively requires net-zero carbon emissions, our prior studies show that using fossil-fueled fuel cells increases costs. This is because additional solar PV and battery storage are needed to offset fossil energy use. As a result, fuel cells are not cost-optimal for ZNE systems unless powered by renewable fuel, which is the basis of our analysis.

Motivation and Objectives: This study seeks to determine whether an SOFC-based ZNE nanogrid can operate as predicted by simulations and whether commercially available controllers can replicate or improve upon optimal energy management strategies. This project aims to:

- Experimentally validate the dynamic operational capabilities of the SOFC and EES when used to power a residential nanogrid.
- Determine if commercially available nanogrid controllers can replicate or improve upon the optimal nanogrid energy system control strategy determined through prior optimization modeling efforts.
- Evaluate the difference between an optimal and heuristics based controls approach at the nanogrid level.

In addition to these objectives, new optimization modeling capabilities have led to quantification of the exact value generated by a SOFC system for a ZNE application, and the evaluation of a SOFC system for low-income ZNE.

Key Findings

- **Marginal Value of SOFCs:** The marginal value of an SOFC system is defined as the additional capital and service contract cost that can be justified by the savings generated from deploying a SOFC. The savings come from two primary sources: (1) reductions in utility bills due to on-site power generation and (2) avoided capital costs for solar PV and battery storage that would otherwise be required to meet ZNE targets. The analysis revealed that SOFCs provide significant value by reducing the capacity requirements of solar PV and battery systems. As shown in **Fig. ES 1**, the marginal value of the first 200 kW of SOFC capacity exceeds \$10,000/kW at hydrogen costs of \$5/kg, due to the

substantial offset in required solar PV and battery capacity. However, marginal value declines sharply as SOFC capacity increases beyond 1 kW, highlighting the importance of system size optimization.

Fig. ES 1: Marginal value of a SOFC system with 50% turndown

- Economic Viability:** SOFC systems are economically viable when hydrogen costs are below \$6/kg and the system costs align with the calculated maximum thresholds. At higher hydrogen costs, the economic feasibility diminishes, making it critical to lower both SOFC capital costs and hydrogen prices for widespread adoption.

Economic Challenges and Opportunities for Low-Income Ratepayers: SOFCs offer limited economic viability for low-income households due to the significant low-income subsidy programs that support solar PV and battery systems. These programs offset over 90% of costs of solar PV and battery storage, enabling low-income ratepayers to achieve ZNE with these technologies alone. Without these subsidies, SOFCs remain viable but at a reduced marginal value, highlighting the need for additional cost reductions in SOFC systems and hydrogen fuel prices to enhance affordability for this demographic.

- Optimal SOFC Operation Repeats Itself:** Optimal SOFC operation oscillates between three modes of operation: 1) the SOFC operates at full power in the morning and evening hours when solar is unavailable, 2) the SOFC operates at minimum load throughout the entire day, and 3) the SOFC operates at maximum load throughout the entire day. These

three modes of operation account for the optimal SOFC operational profile for 351 out of 365 days in the year. The remaining 14 days consist of generation profiles that are necessary for achieving lowest cost ZNE operation despite occurring less than 5% of the year. Representative generation profiles are shown in Fig. ES 2, which also indicates the number of days in a year that are represented with the specific SOFC generation profile.

Fig. ES 2: SOFC generation profiles being used in experiments. Each load profile is representative of a number of days in the year. For example, the top left subfigure load profile represents SOFC operation in 182 days, or nearly 50% of the year.

Experimental Results: Physical testing of a 1.5 kW SOFC showed that the system can respond rapidly to load changes, ramping between minimum and maximum output quickly enough to follow the optimal control profiles generated by the DERopt model. These profiles rely primarily on transitions between full and minimum load, rather than sustained part-load operation. While efficiency during ramping lagged behind power output due to thermal inertia and fuel reforming dynamics, overall results confirm that SOFCs can technically support the operational requirements of a residential ZNE nanogrid. Battery experiments demonstrated even greater flexibility, with near-instantaneous charge and discharge response, confirming that the battery can handle second-to-second balancing while the SOFC provides longer-duration generation.

At the same time, testing revealed critical challenges. The 1.5 kW SOFC proved oversized for typical residential loads, consistent with modeling results that identify optimal capacities below 1 kW. Unexpected derating events reduced maximum output to 1.2 kW without warning, while ancillary component failures—such as non-standard water filters—caused outages. These reliability and integration issues highlight the need for smaller, more robust, and lower-maintenance SOFC units before they can be considered practical for residential ZNE applications.

Control Strategies: Two separate control strategies were evaluated:

- Optimization-based controls, which use technoeconomic optimization to generate dispatch profiles that minimize annual energy costs while meeting ZNE requirements. These controls adapt dynamically to changes in solar availability, building load, utility rates, and fuel costs.
- Heuristic controls, which rely on fixed, rule-based logic (e.g., “run the SOFC at full output unless solar is available” or “discharge the battery during peak export price hours”). These strategies attempt to approximate optimal operation.

Comparison of the two approaches showed that optimization-based controls consistently outperformed heuristics. Replicating optimal dispatch with heuristics required more than 200 unique rules to account for building loads, fuel cell operation, and market conditions, and even then resulted in higher costs. In contrast, optimization-based controls adjusted in real time,

reducing annual ZNE costs by hundreds to thousands of dollars compared to heuristics. The only exception occurred when renewable fuel prices were very low, where the optimal solution simplified to running the SOFC at full output continuously—a strategy easily matched by heuristics.

Conclusion: Overall, these results demonstrate that a SOFC system has sufficient dynamic operating capabilities such that optimal ZNE operation can be achieved with real systems. Most importantly, the SOFC system is capable of ramping between nameplate capacity and minimum load setting within an hour, enabling operation that compliments solar and storage technologies. These results also show that optimization based controls are able to match simulations prior to system installation, showing that lowest cost operation can be achieved in real systems. Finally, the optimal control approach far exceed simple heuristics based controls by consistently pushing the fuel cell towards lowest cost operation. These results demonstrate that smart, optimization-based controls are essential for cost-effective ZNE operation, and that true interoperability between SOFCs, batteries, and solar systems is a critical enabler for their residential deployment.

These results were generated using commercially available nanogrid controller technology. This technology was initially developed for larger scale microgrid operation optimization. A key requirement for successful deployment at the nanogrid scale is controller cost, which currently exceeds the total cost of the experimental setup. However, this is due, in part, to the novel nature of the research requiring custom algorithm development for the nanogrid controller. Since residential rates are the same for entire regions, and the energy loads for different residential loads can be characterized using a combination of building energy modeling, statistical methods, and machine learning, we hypothesize that the cost of the controller systems used in this effort represent the research and development costs incurred by the commercially available controller technology, and that subsequent system costs will be lower.

All of this considered, the key for SOFCs to be a ZNE solution is the availability of renewable fuel. At renewable fuel prices equivalent to \$6/kg H₂ or lower (with \$2/kg being most favorable), SOFCs are the preferred ZNE technology due to their high efficiency, ability to avoid large and costly storage systems, and continuous power production. In this scenario, SOFC adoption should be pursued as part of the residential ZNE pathway.

Nomenclature

The nomenclature section summarizes general abbreviations, terms of art, and acronyms used throughout this report. This list does not include variables and parameters used in the optimization model.

ATS	Automatic transfer switch
CARE	California Alternative Rates for Energy
CEC	California Energy Commission
CHP	Combined heat and power
DAC-SASH	Disadvantaged Communities – Single Family Solar Homes Program
ELF	Engineering Laboratory Facility
ESS	Energy storage system
MILP	Mixed integer linear program
PEMFC	Proton exchange membrane fuel cell
PV	Photovoltaic
SGIP	Self Generation Incentive Program
SOFC	Solid oxide fuel cell
TDV	Time Dependent Value
ZNE	Zero net energy

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Background

This study aims to explore the potential of combining gas systems, solid oxide fuel cells (SOFC), solar photovoltaics (PV), and battery storage to achieve zero net energy (ZNE) in residential nanogrids¹. The general layout of this system is shown in Figure 1. The hypothesis is that integrating gas and electrical systems can meet the thermal and electricity needs of ZNE homes more cost-effectively than full electrification.

Figure 1: Schematic of the general DER layout considered in this work

ZNE is defined in various ways. In California, it means net zero carbon emissions for a building energy use. The state's 2008 regulation requires new and retrofitted homes to achieve ZNE by 2020, using a metric called time-dependent value of electricity (TDV) [1]. The TDV calculates fossil fuel use for electricity and natural gas every hour, from 2022 to 2052, to determine ZNE [2]. A building is ZNE if its total fossil energy use equals zero. TDV also includes utility-independent

¹ A "nanogrid" refers to a small-scale, localized energy system that can operate independently from or in parallel with a larger power grid. It is typically limited to a single building that has generation, storage, and load control technologies. For this report, a nanogrid refers to an individual residence.

retail costs for energy, assessing the impact of modifications needed to meet ZNE.

As of 2024, few homes are ZNE, and the ZNE mandate is not enforced due to cost concerns. Any ZNE measures must be cost-effective, according to the TDV definition. If not, the California Energy Commission (CEC) cannot require them. Additionally, ZNE's cost impact can affect energy equity, as nearly 30% of California's ratepayers are low-income, many facing energy burdens of 5% or more [3,4]. Rising costs to meet ZNE could disproportionately impact these households.

This study focuses on SOFC technology as a potential low-cost ZNE solution. SOFCs are particularly promising because they offer high fuel-to-electricity conversion efficiency, produce high-temperature exhaust gases for combined heat and power (CHP) applications, have long lifespans, and are available in residential sizes (<5 kW). SOFCs' high operating temperatures reduce electrochemical losses compared to other fuel cell technologies and allow for the use of exhaust heat in domestic hot water systems. While many fuel cell products are shifting to larger capacities, smaller SOFC and PEMFC systems (100s to 1000s of watts) remain available. PEMFCs are less attractive due to shorter stack lifespans (~10,000 hours), while SOFCs typically operate for 5–10 years without requiring stack replacement.

UCI has previously researched the application of SOFC systems for ZNE homes². Key findings from this prior work are:

- SOFC as a ZNE technology is economically feasible only if powered using renewable fuel. These results were based on the assumption that renewable H₂ is available at costs ranging from \$4.50 to \$6/kg H₂. SOFC systems are economically feasible primarily due avoided solar PV and EES costs.
- Even though a renewable gas powered SOFC helps achieve a lower cost ZNE house in 2045, the building still needs to be first electrified with efficient heat pumps.
- From a ZNE perspective, SOFC operation is “energy-neutral” when using a fully renewable fuel. As a result, export from a SOFC during periods when grid electricity has a

² The final report for the prior work can be found at: <https://zenodo.org/records/10904120>

high TDV energy value results in net negative energy use, which can offset fossil energy use during other periods.

This research effort includes a theoretical and experimental component. The purpose of the theoretical component is to quantify the value of using a SOFC in a residential ZNE application, and to determine the cost and size at which this system is economically viable. The purpose of the experimental effort is to test if the optimal operation prescribed by UCI models is feasible, and if commercial energy system control technologies approach optimal operation. This work builds off of the prior work by:

1. Experimentally verifying the capabilities of real SOFC and EES systems to perform as prescribed by prior ZNE optimization models.

This work also adds to the knowledge developed in prior optimization efforts by using new simulation features to:

2. Quantify the value of a SOFC as a ZNE technology as a function of fuel cell size and fuel cost.
3. Compare SOFC systems to lower temperature PEMFC systems as a ZNE solution.
4. Evaluate the value of SOFC as a ZNE technology for low income rate payers.

1.2 Report Layout

The report is split into three sections:

- Section 2 summarizes the modeling tools and data used throughout this report.
- Section 3 presents key findings from the theoretical analysis carried out during this project.
- Section 4 discusses experimental efforts to examine the dynamic capabilities of the SOFC and residential battery systems.
- Section 5 compares the cost impacts of optimal versus heuristic control methods for achieving ZNE.
- Section 6 provides a discussion and review of project results.

- Section 7 summarizes the work and concludes the report..

2 Assumptions, Data Sources, and Methods

This section describes the different data sources used to simulate, analyze, and experiment based on a theoretical house located in Southern California. The data described in this section was used during prior optimization efforts, and will also be used in experimental efforts to simulate electricity and gas demands for a real house.

There are 16 different climate zones across California. However, the most populous climate zones across California have a similar climates, including similar number of heating and cooling days [5]. To simplify our analysis, we focus our analysis on Climate Zone 6, which has a Los Angeles as the reference city.

2.1 Assumptions

Key assumptions made in this work include:

- **Availability of renewable H₂:** We assume that renewable H₂, or some other renewable gaseous fuel, is available for use by residential utility customers. Our prior work found that SOFC systems for ZNE applications are viable only if renewable fuel is available. Otherwise, SOFC systems are not cost effective for ZNE applications.
- **Extension of CARE rates to renewable fuels:** Low-income ratepayers in California have access to California Alternate Rates for Energy (CARE) rates, which reduce the retail of electricity by ~33%, and natural gas by ~20%. We assume that the 20% gas rate reduction applies when switching over to renewable fuels.
- **Deterministic operation:** Optimal control methods operate with foreknowledge of future residential energy demands.
- **Utility connection:** ZNE homes are connected to both electric and gas utilities and can draw energy from either service.

2.2 Building Energy Loads

Building energy loads used in this work are based on building energy model outputs developed in our prior SOFC ZNE work [6]. The geometry, layout and envelope specifications for the building energy model is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: One-story single family detached prototype BEM specification and model overview. Subfigures show (a) building exterior [7] and (c) floor plan [7], and the corresponding BEM (b and d).

Our prior work found that the lowest cost solution for achieving ZNE requires the electrification of space and water heating systems using high efficiency heat pumps. For this work, we assume that the home is equipped with high performance heat pump systems for space and water heating. The space heating system is an air-sourced, mini-split heat pump system operating at 29.3 seasonal energy efficiency ratio and 14 heating seasonal performance factor [8–10]. The water heater is 50 gallon heat pump water heater operating with a uniform energy factor of 3.0. The heat pump water heater is located in the garage. All other appliances, plug loads, and lighting definitions were matched to the same values used in prior work. Resulting average electrical demand for each quarter in the year is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Average electrical demand for the building energy model simulation

2.3 Electric and Gas Utility Rates

This work uses current Southern California Edison retail residential utility time-of-use rates [11] augmented using cost projections based on initial projections associated with reaching California environmental goals [12]. Utility gas rates are based on residential natural gas rates through Southern California Gas company. Natural gas rates consist of transmission and distribution, and procurement costs. While transmission and distribution costs have remained stable over the past decade, procurement costs can vary widely month to month. Instead of developing a projection of gas prices, procurement cost assumed to be the average price of procurement between 2010 and 2020, or approximately \$0.40 per therm [13].

Both Southern California Edison and Southern California Gas offer discounted rates to households with incomes at or below 200% of federal poverty limits [14,15]. These rates, known as California

Alternative Rates for Energy (CARE) rates, reduce utility electricity rates by ~30%, and gas rates by ~20%.

One advancement made in this work are electricity export rates. During our prior work, the California Public Utilities Commission was in the process of developing, proposing, and accepting new rates for the export of electricity from residential customers. These efforts yielded the current Net Energy Metering 3.0 rates, which are based on the typical value of wholesale electricity for an electric utility. These export rates offer far less value than prior Net Energy Metering 2.0 rates, which were based on retail electricity prices. As a result, the California Public Utilities Commission authorized an additional bonus of \$0.04/kWh exported under Net Energy Metering 3.0 for customers who install solar PV in the next few years. This bonus increases to \$0.09/kWh for low-income ratepayers who qualify for CARE rates.

2.4 DERopt Review and Developments

DERopt is a technoeconomic optimization model designed to find the lowest cost solution for meeting a given electrical demand. When economically desirable, DERopt will propose the adoption of electricity generators and storage technologies, and indicate how these components should be operated in order to achieve lowest cost. DERopt is a mixed integer linear program (MILP). The MILP structure is well suited for technoeconomic optimization of energy systems because it resolves both continuous and discrete decisions (e.g., generator power setting vs. on/off status) and can be used to capture nonlinear systems through piece-wise linearization approaches. The general MILP structure includes a cost function that includes operational and equipment purchase decisions (x in Equations (1)) subject to technoeconomic constraints (Equations (2) and (3)) where some variables must take integer values (x_i , in Equation (4)). A complete mathematical description of DERopt is provided in the Appendix.

$$\text{minimize } C^T x \tag{1}$$

$$\tag{2}$$

$$\text{such that } Ax < b \tag{3}$$

$$x_i \in \mathbb{Z} \tag{4}$$

If the integer variables in DERopt are converted to continuous linear variables, the resulting linear program provides additional insights not available with the traditional MILP formulation. One key piece of information is the "shadow price" associated with each constraint in the optimization model. The shadow price indicates how the optimal solution's cost would change if the constraint were adjusted. This value represents the marginal impact of modifying model parameters. For example, consider Equation (5) where $e_{Fuel\ Cell,t}$ represents electricity generated from a fuel cell at time t , and $P_{Fuel\ Cell}$ represents the fuel cell capacity in kilowatts (kW). This equation is a constraint limiting the electrical output from a fuel cell by the installed capacity. The shadow price associated with Equation (5) indicates how much the total cost (utility bills, equipment capital, and operations and maintenance) will change if fuel cell capacity changes by ± 1 kW. If the fuel cell cost is set to zero, the shadow price reflects potential cost savings from reduced utility bills and avoided investment in alternative technologies. A fuel cell is economically viable if its purchase, installation, and maintenance costs are lower than this shadow price. Thus, the marginal value of the fuel cell equals the shadow price, and the fuel cell will be adopted in the optimal system configuration if its total cost is below this marginal value.

$$e_{Fuel\ Cell,t} \leq P_{Fuel\ Cell} \quad (5)$$

For this study, the shadow price is used to analyze: (a) the marginal value of an SOFC system in a ZNE application, and (b) the maximum allowable cost for a commercially available residential SOFC where its adoption remains economically justifiable.

To calculate the shadow price, SOFC capacity is first limited, and its capital cost is set to zero. DERopt is then solved with this capacity limit, and the shadow price is extracted. The model is subsequently solved again with a slightly higher capacity limit, and this process continues until the shadow price drops to zero, indicating that further increases in SOFC capacity no longer provide value. These results show how other costs—such as utility bills or reduced capital costs from smaller solar PV or battery systems—change as SOFC capacity increases.

Theoretically, the SOFC capital cost could approach or equal the shadow price and still be economically viable. However, if the capital cost exceeds this threshold, the SOFC becomes economically unfeasible.

The key advancement in DERopt is the utilization of this shadow price in evaluating the economic viability of different energy technologies. For this particular work, this concept is applied to understand how the value of a SOFC changes under different circumstances:

- **Conventional SOFC Operating at Part Load:** This scenario assesses the value of commercially available residential SOFC systems, helping establish the price target required for economic viability when the system operates at less than full capacity.
- **Conventional SOFC Operating at Full Load:** This examines the value of a SOFC system that must operate at full load, exploring whether the ability to dynamically adjust output justifies potential degradation from frequent ramping (e.g., wear on the system due to cycling).
- **SOFC Installed in Residences with Gas Heating:** The core analysis assumes an electrified home, but this scenario investigates whether the SOFC's value is influenced by whether the home uses gas heating or is fully electrified.
- **SOFC Value for Low-Income Ratepayers:** This analysis determines if the economic value of SOFCs holds for low-income households. It also helps identify whether financial support programs are needed and what the minimum subsidy would be to make the SOFC economically viable for these households.
- **Value of Alternative Fuel Cell Technologies:** This compares the value of SOFCs to other fuel cell types, specifically proton exchange membrane fuel cells (PEMFCs), which have lower efficiency and exhaust temperatures but offer more dynamic operation (e.g., the ability to shut down and restart easily).

2.5 Equipment Costs

Equipment costs are based on costs used in our prior work. A summary of these cost items is listed in Table 8 in Appendix A.

Two factors that affect low-income ZNE operation are programs that support the development of clean generation and storage for low income ratepayers:

- Disadvantaged Communities – Single Family Solar Homes Program (DAC-SASH) is a program that supports the development of solar on low-income single-family buildings.

DAC-SASH provides up to \$3,000/kW rebate on solar PV for customers who qualify for utility CARE rates and live in areas designated as environmentally disadvantaged by the California specific tool CalEnviroScreen.

- Self-Generation Incentive Program (SGIP) Equity provides up to \$850/kWh support for income qualifying rate payers to install battery energy storage on their property. Battery sizes are limited to 10 kWh per residential unit

2.6 Time Dependent Valuation of Energy

The current work is focused on residential energy use that drives fossil energy use in California, which is captured in the TDV for energy. The TDV metric was developed to understand how the fossil content and value of electricity, natural gas, and other energy sources and emissions from these sources change throughout the year on an hourly basis. A component of this metric includes primary energy use for the different energy sources, or the quantity of fossil resources required for the delivery of utility electricity and natural gas. The primary energy TDV value of natural gas is constant throughout the year at 1.0166 kBtu per 1.0 kBtu natural gas used onsite (the TDV value of natural gas is higher than the delivered energy due to transmission and distribution losses). The TDV value of electricity varies depending on time of day and across seasons. This metric is summarized for the quarters of the year in Figure 4. This figure shows the average hourly TDV primary energy required to deliver 1.0 kWh of electricity. TDV energy trends with solar potential – TDV energy is lowest during daytime, and the spring quarter has the lowest overall TDV energy value due to the high levels of renewable electricity production.

Figure 4: Average primary energy intensity for grid electricity in California, according to the TDV of energy [16]. Results are presented based on quarterly average across the calendar year. The lowest energy intensity occurs during Q2, or from April to June, and the highest occurs during Q1 and Q4, or October through March. These results are related to renewable resource availability.

3 Evaluation of SOFC Value

This section uses the DERopt model to estimate the economic value of the SOFC system by quantifying the potential savings from its installation and operation. These savings come from reduced utility bills and avoided investment in solar and battery systems otherwise required to meet zero net energy goals.

For the SOFC system to be economically viable, system installed and operating costs must be lower than these potential savings. If not, the cost-optimal path to zero net energy will rely solely on solar and battery storage. Therefore, the estimated savings define the maximum allowable SOFC system cost for it to be a recommended investment.

This study builds on that work by quantifying the concept, determining the maximum acceptable cost for economic viability, and identifying the optimal size of the SOFC that delivers value for a ZNE application. This section relies on the “shadow price” concept described in Section 2.4. All results are based on the assumption that the SOFC is being introduced into a situation where ZNE is required. Prior to SOFC adoption, ZNE is achieved almost exclusively through the adoption of solar PV and battery energy storage.

3.1 Value of Dynamic SOFC

The premise that a controller can and should be designed to operate a SOFC based ZNE energy system relies on the assumption that a SOFC can and should be operated dynamically.

Commercially available SOFC systems are typically designed for steady-state operation. Our prior ZNE efforts indirectly showed that SOFC systems with dynamic generation capabilities are more valuable than SOFCs that must be ran at steady state. In this section, we compare a SOFC system with a 50% turndown capability (operating between 50% and 100% of rated capacity) to one with a 5% turndown capability (operating between 95% and 100% of rated capacity). The analysis also identifies the maximum acceptable cost for SOFC systems in ZNE applications. The analysis depends on cost of hydrogen, which is varied between \$0.50/kg and \$8/kg H₂.

The marginal value of a SOFC system with 50% turndown versus H₂ cost and system size is shown in Figure 5. This figure shows the marginal value changing as both H₂ and SOFC capacity

changes. For example, at \$5/kg H₂, the first 200W of fuel cell capacity is has a marginal value³ between \$14,000 and \$12,000/kW. SOFC system capacity has such great value at this level primarily due to reductions in solar PV and battery energy storage capacity, which are shown in Figure 6 and Figure 7. According to these results, the first 200 W of SOFC capacity decreases solar PV capacity by 1 kW and battery capacity by nearly 10 kWh.

Figure 5: Marginal value of a SOFC system with 50% turndown

The marginal value of SOFC systems remains relatively stable above \$10,000 for capacities between 200W and 500W but decreases sharply as capacity increases from 500W to 1 kW. This decline in value is primarily due to the continued need for solar PV and battery energy storage to achieve cost-optimal ZNE operation. Furthermore, as shown in Figure 5, the marginal value of

³ Marginal value for the SOFC is the maximum fuel cell capital and maintenance cost that is economically viable in a residential ZNE application. Refer to Section 2.4 for a complete description

SOFC systems is highly sensitive to hydrogen prices. For instance, increasing the hydrogen cost from \$2/kg to \$8/kg results in a 75% to 90% reduction in SOFC value. These results suggest that for residential ZNE applications, the maximum SOFC system size should be 1 kW if H₂ costs drop below \$3/kg and significantly smaller at higher costs.

Figure 6: Optimal solar PV capacity that corresponds to Figure 5

Figure 7: Optimal battery capacity that corresponds to Figure 5

Figure 8 illustrates the marginal value of a SOFC with a 5% turndown capability. The results

show that its overall value is lower compared to a SOFC with a 50% turndown capability. Additionally, the figure indicates that the capacity at which increasing SOFC size no longer adds value lies between 600W and 800W—significantly below the typical capacities of commercially available residential SOFC systems, which are around 1,500W.

Figure 8: Marginal value of a SOFC system with 5% turndown

Both marginal value figures highlight a point where increasing SOFC size no longer provides additional value. Figure 9 identifies these capacity thresholds for SOFC systems with 50% and 5% turndown capabilities. For instance, with a 50% turndown and hydrogen priced at \$3/kg, the maximum cost-effective SOFC size peaks at 1 kW. Beyond this capacity, increasing SOFC size does not reduce the cost of achieving ZNE. In fact, if a larger SOFC size leads to a higher

minimum load, its value can decrease.

Figure 9: SOFC capacity where there is no value in increasing system power output

Integrating these marginal value results produces the maximum fuel cell system cost that is economically viable⁴. The results from this integration are shown in Figure 10, which show the maximum SOFC system cost for a 50% and 5% turndown SOFC versus H₂ cost.

⁴ Economic viability indicates the point at which the adoption of a SOFC lowers the cost of achieving ZNE. Increasing system cost would make the system uneconomic, meaning that a solar PV and storage solution is lower cost.

Figure 10: Maximum installed SOFC cost at which the system is economically viable in a residential ZNE application

The SOFC system used in the experimental setup (Section 4.1.2) has a capacity of 1.5 kW. These results indicate that the SOFC system is oversized for residential applications by 20% to 50%, depending on fuel cost. In practice, commercially available SOFC systems are not available at power levels less than 1.5 kW, limiting experimental options to SOFC systems that are oversized for the residential application.

3.2 Value of SOFC for Electrified vs. Gas Space and Water Heating

Previous analyses⁵ have shown that the lowest cost of energy is achieved when residential buildings are electrified and distributed energy resources (such as solar PV, battery storage, and SOFCs) are adopted in combination. This section examines these findings in detail. The SOFC optimization results presented here assume a system with a 50% turndown capability.

We evaluated the marginal value of SOFCs based on hydrogen cost and SOFC size, identifying the maximum economically feasible SOFC size and corresponding system cost. The maximum SOFC size for powering a single-family home with gas space and water heating was found to be nearly identical to that for a fully electrified home. Figure 11 shows the maximum system costs for SOFCs in both scenarios.

⁵ Please refer to <https://zenodo.org/records/10904120>

Figure 11: Maximum fuel cell system cost when a SOFC is used to provide heat and electricity to a single-family home that has been electrified or uses gas space and water heating.

The results indicate that when hydrogen costs are below \$6/kg, SOFC systems can have a higher cost when installed in electrified homes. This outcome is tied to the primary value drivers of SOFC systems at smaller capacities. As shown in the previous section, the marginal value of an SOFC system below 200W exceeds \$10,000/kW because SOFC adoption reduces the need for solar PV and battery capacity.

In homes with gas-based space and water heating, electrical demand is lower, leading to smaller solar PV and battery requirements prior to SOFC adoption. Consequently, when an SOFC is introduced in these homes, it offsets a smaller solar PV and battery system compared to fully electrified homes, where the demand for electricity is higher.

However, these results also indicate that when cost of hydrogen exceeds \$6/kg, SOFCs used at homes with gas space and water heating are more valuable. This result is not as significant as for SOFC costs at <\$6/kg H₂ since higher H₂ costs translate to smaller SOFC size, higher ZNE costs, and the increased likelihood that complete electrification is the lower cost solution.

3.3 Value of SOFC to Low Income Rate Payers

Two low-income scenarios are considered: with and without DAC-SASH and SGIP equity support for solar PV and battery storage, respectively. Both scenarios use CARE rates for utility electricity, natural gas, and H₂, resulting in a 33% reduction in retail electricity rates and a 20%

reduction in retail natural gas and H₂ rates. We assume that the CARE rates extend to H₂, reducing the cost of H₂ by 20%:

- When DAC-SASH and SGIP equity funds are available, SOFCs are completely uneconomic. DAC-SASH and SGIP equity funds offset >90% of solar and battery costs. Since DAC-SASH program rules allow solar PV systems that completely offset electricity, low income rate payers can install sufficient solar capacity to completely offset their electrical demand. Additionally, SGIP-equity reduces battery costs by 70% to 90%, reducing much of the financial burden associated with installing energy shifting capabilities. The result is a low cost solar PV and battery system more than capable of achieving ZNE. In this instance, installing a SOFC at any cost will increase total cost of energy for low-income ratepayers.
- Accessing DAC-SASH and SGIP equity funds requires:
 - Residents must meet income eligibility requirements⁶
 - Home ownership.
 - In some cases, whole building energy efficiency and electrification prior to funding solar and storage projects.
 - Availability of DAC-SASH and SGIP Equity programs, which depends on funding allocations from the California state budget, cap-and-trade revenues, and/or utility ratepayer-supported programs.

When a residential customer is ineligible for DAC-SASH or SGIP Equity funding, annual funding is fully allocated, or the programs are reduced or eliminated in future State budgets, SOFC value results for low-income ratepayers are nearly identical to results shown in Section 3.1. However, since CARE rates reduce the cost of utility electricity, SOFC value is lower by \$250 - \$400/kW.

⁶ Typically, this is 200% federal poverty limits

4 ZNE Experiments

The purpose of the experimental effort is to test if the optimal operation prescribed by UCI models is feasible, and if commercial energy system control technologies approach optimal operation. Experimental efforts include analysis of optimal ZNE operation, the construction of a ZNE experiment, implementation of ZNE residential energy system control software and hardware, and a comparison of experimental results versus optimal operation predicted by DERopt.

An example of optimal SOFC/solar PV/EES storage is shown in Figure 12 and Figure 13. These figures show optimal operation for the same week. Figure 12 shows optimal SOFC, solar PV, and EES storage (EES storage includes both a conventional battery – EES - and a battery exclusively charged by renewable resources – REES). Figure 13 shows the corresponding solar PV production and battery charging/discharging. Figure 13 includes the TDV energy intensity of the electric grid throughout the day. Optimal ZNE operation primarily focuses on managing energy flows to and from the building based on TDV energy intensity. Figure 12 illustrates midday electricity imports when TDV energy costs are low (Figure 13), primarily to charge batteries. At the same time, solar energy charges storage and exports excess power to the grid once batteries are full. As TDV energy intensity rises in the early evening, both batteries discharge. Electricity stored from grid imports supplies building loads, while solar-charged battery power is exported to the grid. During daylight hours, the SOFC operates at minimum load. As the sun sets and batteries deplete, the SOFC ramps up to full power, following the remaining building load until sunrise.

Figure 12: Example of optimal SOFC, solar, and battery energy storage (EES and REES)

Figure 13: Example of solar and EES/REES operation compared to the TDV energy signal

In general, the desired operation includes:

- Reducing SOFC operation whenever onsite solar PV is productive and/or utility electricity TDV energy intensity is near zero. As solar PV production wanes, ramp the fuel cell up to follow building electric demand, reducing output whenever batteries discharge at

opportune instances to send electricity back to the grid when utility electricity TDV energy intensity is high.

- Use batteries to absorb electricity when the TDV energy intensity for the electric grid is low and when there is excess solar, followed by discharging when electric grid TDV energy intensity is high. If the battery was charged using solar PV, export electricity back to the grid, resulting in a negative TDV energy balance.

4.1 Experimental Setup

The goal of the experimental setup is to physically replicate the system shown in Figure 1, , which consists of an SOFC, a solar PV system, and a battery energy storage system, all operating in parallel with the electric grid to meet both electrical and thermal demand for a single house. A high-level technology layout, one-line diagram, and communications diagram for the experimental setup are provided in Figure 14.

Figure 14: One-line and communications diagram showing the layout of the SOFC, solar PV, and battery energy systems when connected to an electrical load that simulates a residential building in CZ06. ELF 140 and 134F tags indicate the location of the test equipment inside the Engineering Laboratory Facility at UC Irvine, or ELF

In this experiment, an AC load simulator (Chroma 63803) is used to generate electrical demand that aligns with the energy consumption predictions from the building energy model presented in

Section 2.1. The load simulator is connected to a 1.5 kW SOFC, a simulated 5 kW solar PV array, and a battery energy system. The components are interconnected using wiring setups that are typical for residential applications. Due to the different phase requirements for the system components and varying phase service availability within the UCI laboratory, the individual components were installed in two separate locations within the building⁷. The following sections describe the individual components used in the experimental setup.

4.1.1 Load Simulators

Chroma 63804 programmable AC load simulators are used to simulate the electrical demand from a house. The Chroma 63804 Programmable AC/DC Electronic Load has a power rating of 4,500 W, a voltage range of 50–350 V_{rms} (500 V_{peak}), and a current range of 0–45 Arms (135 A_{peak}). The device operates at frequencies from 45–440 Hz. The residential operation loads are supplied by running two Chroma 63804 in parallel operation, with two units supporting up to 9 kW. The Chromas simulate loads using the same data that the DC supply uses to replicate solar output. Complete specifications for the Chroma 63804 is shown in Figure 15. This figure is of the technical specifications for the Chroma 6380x model, with includes two lower power AC load simulators.

⁷ The solar PV and SOFC system output single phase electricity, while the battery system requires a connection to a two-phase system. Both types of electricity are typically available in all California homes, but were not available in the same room at the UCI research facilities. This configuration will not affect experimental results since experiments focus on individual system potential to respond to control signal inputs from a nanogrid controller, not how the electrical outputs from the components interact on a power quality level.

SPECIFICATION			
Model	63802	63803	63804
Power	1,800W	3,600W	4,500W
Current	0 - 18A _{rms} (54 A _{peak})	0 - 36A _{rms} (108 A _{peak})	0 - 45A _{rms} (135 A _{peak})
Voltage	50 - 350V _{rms} (500 V _{peak})	50 - 350V _{rms} (500 V _{peak})	50 - 350V _{rms} (500 V _{peak})
Frequency	45 - 440Hz, DC	45 - 440Hz, DC	45 - 440Hz, DC
AC Section			
Constant Current Mode			
Range	0 - 18A _{rms} , Programmable	0 - 36A _{rms} , Programmable	0 - 45A _{rms} , Programmable
Accuracy ¹	0.1% + 0.2%F.S.	0.1% + 0.2%F.S.	0.1% + 0.2%F.S.
Resolution	2mA	5mA	5mA
Constant Resistance Mode			
Range	2.77Ω - 2.5kΩ, Programmable	1.39Ω - 2.5kΩ, Programmable	1.11Ω - 2.5kΩ, Programmable
Accuracy	0.5% + 0.5%F.S.	0.5% + 0.5%F.S.	0.5% + 0.5%F.S.
Resolution ⁴	20μS	50μS	50μS
Constant Power Mode			
Range	1,800W, Programmable	3,600W, Programmable	4,500W, Programmable
Accuracy	0.2% + 0.3%F.S.	0.2% + 0.3%F.S.	0.2% + 0.3%F.S.
Resolution	0.375W	1.125W	1.125W
Crest Factor (under CC, CP modes)			
Range ²	1,414 - 5.0, Programmable	1,414 - 5.0, Programmable	1,414 - 5.0, Programmable
Accuracy	(0.5% / I _{max}) + 1% F.S.	(0.5% / I _{max}) + 1% F.S.	(0.5% / I _{max}) + 1% F.S.
Resolution	0.005	0.005	0.005
Power Factor			
Range	0 - 1 lead or lag, Programmable	0 - 1 lead or lag, Programmable	0 - 1 lead or lag, Programmable
Accuracy	1%F.S.	1%F.S.	1%F.S.
Resolution	0.001	0.001	0.001
Rectified Load Mode			
Operating Frequency	45Hz - 70Hz		
RLC mode	Parameter: L _i (max), R _i , L _s , C, R _s		
Constant Power Mode	Parameter: L _i (max), Power setting = 200W - 1,800W, PF = 0.4 - 0.75	Parameter: L _i (max), Power setting = 200W - 3,600W, PF = 0.4 - 0.75	Parameter: L _i (max), Power setting = 200W - 4,500W, PF = 0.4 - 0.75
Inrush Current Mode	Parameter: L _i (max), R _i , L _s , C, R _s , Phase		
	80A (peak current)	160A (peak current)	200A (peak current)
R _i Range	0 - 9,999Ω	0 - 9,999Ω	0 - 9,999Ω
L _s Range	0 - 9999μH	0 - 9999μH	0 - 9999μH
C Range	100 - 9999μF	100 - 9999μF	100 - 9999μF
R _s Range	2.77 - 9999.99Ω	1.39 - 9999.99Ω	1.11 - 9999.99Ω
DC Section			
Voltage Range	7.5V - 500V	7.5V - 500V	7.5V - 500V
Current Range	0A - 18A	0A - 36A	0A - 45A

Figure 15: Specifications for the Chroma 63804 programmable load simulators (63804 is in the right column)

Figure 16: Chroma load banks stationed

4.1.2 SOFC

The SOFC used in this experimental setup is the SolidPower BlueGEN™. The BlueGEN system is a SOFC CHP system that can provide 1.5 kW electricity at a 55% fuel to electricity conversion efficiency. Exhaust gases can be routed through an air-to-water heat exchanger to produce domestic hot water. Heat recovery at 1.5 kW electrical output is approximately 0.54 kW thermal, leading to an overall fuel utilization of 75%. In practice, fuel utilization can be boosted by manipulating water flow and temperature in the air-to-water heat exchanger – utilization can be boosted when water flow rates are slowed and/or when water inlet temperatures are low.

Figure 17: The BlueGEN SOFC system used in the nano-grid demonstration project

An older BlueGEN 15 stack was tested over a 24-hour power cycle, as depicted in Figure 18. The testing demonstrated the effect of 42 days of operation, equivalent to 1,000 hours, under highly dynamic operating conditions. A degradation rate of 0.58% was noted, corresponding to a voltage loss of approximately 4.7 mV per cell. As shown in Figure 19, the V-j characteristics curves compare the first and last days of the test, highlighting the changes in performance.

During the initial 1,000 hours of operation, when the system was new, the degradation rate was observed to be twice as high as that under steady-state conditions. Findings state that as the stack performance declines, fuel consumption increases, leading to a reduction in overall system efficiency. This emphasizes the relationship between degradation and system efficiency losses over time, particularly under fluctuating operational conditions.

Figure 18: Power Cycle of BlueGEN stack 24-hour cycle

Figure 19: V-j characteristics curve for 24-hour power cycle for 42 days

Despite 5 years of operation, the SOFC stack has degraded minimally, and nominal output power is still near 1.5 kW. This older BlueGEN system used to generate Figure 18 and Figure 19 was decommissioned and a newer SolidPower BlueGEN 15 will be used for this experimental effort.

4.1.3 Solar PV

The existing solar PV array on top of UCI laboratory facilities has degraded sufficiently to be of limited value for experimental efforts. In place, solar PV is simulated by using a programmable DC power supply to power a solar PV inverter. The solar PV inverter used in this work is a KACO Blueplanet 5002xi/x inverter. Specifications for the Blueplanet line of inverters is shown in Figure 21.

Figure 20: The Chroma 62050H-600S DC Supply

Model number	blueplanet 1502xi/x	blueplanet 2502xi/x	blueplanet 3502xi/x	blueplanet 5002xi/x
DC Electrical Specifications				
Max. DC input voltage (VDC)	550	550	600	600
DC maximum peak power (MPP) operating range (VDC)	125-400	200-450	200-510	200-510
DC operating range (VDC)	125-550	200-550	200-550	200-550
DC minimum start voltage (VDC)	125	200	200	200
DC maximum operating current (ADC)	14.3	13.5	18.5	26.5
DC maximum short circuit current (ADC)	21.5	21.5	28	40
Maximum input source backfeed current (ADC)	0	0	0	0
DC input overload protection	Voltage and current limiting during operation			
DC input terminals / conductor size per channel A - B	3 Pos and 3 Neg 4-12 AWG Al Cu			
AC Electrical Specifications				
AC max continuous output power (W)	1500	2500	3500	5000
CEC weighted efficiency (%) (240 / 208 VAC)	95.5/95	95.5/95	95.5/95	95.5/95
AC nominal voltage / operating range L to Neutral (VAC)	240 (211 -264) / 208 (184-226)			
AC Continuous output current (A) (240 / 208 VAC)	6.25 / 7.2	10.4 / 12.0	14.6 / 16.8	20.8 / 24
AC branch circuit protection (A)	10 / 10	15 / 15	20 / 25	30 / 30
Frequency nominal / range (Hz)	60 / 60.5 to 59.3			
Power factor	>.99			
Total harmonic distortion %	< 5			
Standby losses (W)	< 0.3			
AC input terminals and conductor	3 / 4-12 AWG Al Cu			
Maximum output fault current (AC) and duration (A AC) (µs)	30 / 100	50 / 100	70 / 100	96 / 100
AC synchronization in-rush current (A AC)	< 0.5			

Figure 21: Technical specifications for the KACO Blueplanet inverter(5002xi/x is in the far right column)

The KACO Blueplanet 5002xi/x inverter specifies a DC maximum power point tracking operating range of 200-510 V DC and a maximum operating current of 26.5 A DC. Based on the rewired configuration of the solar array where the operational voltage is rated at 396 V DC and the operational current is rated at 15.6 A DC, the inverter can safely be used to continuously output 5 kW AC.

DC power input to the KACO Blueplanet 5002xi/x inverter is supplied by a Chroma 62050H-600S programable DC power supply. This 5 kW programmable DC power supply has an output range of 0–600 V and 0–8.5 A. The device provides a controlled and programmable replacement for incoming solar power. Solar profiles for cloudy and sunny days were programmed in five minute increments using a linear interpolation method to switch between hourly or minute solar profile data to the five minute data used in the DC power supply. Solar profiles for CZ06 were taken from the National Solar Radiation Data Base [17]. Emulating solar profiles using linear

interpolation loses the dynamics of solar PV that may potentially impact overall SOFC/solar PV/storage operation. However, the effect should be relatively small since the interpolated profiles represent an equivalent amount of solar energy that would fall on a real panel.

Additionally, while the sun is out, optimal SOFC operation typically requires for the fuel cell to be set to minimum load – solar dynamics during a generally sunny day do not affect this result.

4.1.4 Battery

A LG AC coupled 5 kW energy storage system was purchased for the purpose of this project and future experiments. The purchase includes the following components: battery pack, inverter, automatic transfer switch (ATS), and energy meter. However, for the scope of this project, islanding of the Nano-grid system is not necessary since we are not simulating a utility outage that will require ATS operation, and energy measurements are taken through external equipment. Thus, the ATS and energy meter were not installed. The battery pack and inverter have been mounted within the experimental location of this project, ELF 134f. Progress on experiments was hindered in the following year. The inverter purchased is a model that was discontinued, which resulted in many unresolvable obstacles—including being unable to access the device’s communication protocols for controls.

While the manufacturer failed to provide the necessary documents to establish communication, the controls technology company we partnered with, Heila Technologies, donated the same battery and a SolarEdge SE7600A-US battery inverter. The inverter has a max AC power output of 8350 kW, a maximum continuous output current at 240V of 32 amps, and a max DC power (STC) of 10250 W. The inverter is compatible with our system, but required 3 phase 120/208 WYE to split phase transformer to connect to the laboratory facility electrical network. Installing the ESS with the new SolarEdge inverter in a different laboratory space that has a split-phase connection to the grid bypassed the more expenses at the cost of splitting our system into two rooms. The battery and inverter are connected by 120/208 3 phase WYE, while the inverter connects to a 208 to 230 step-up transformer. Figure 22 shows the mounted LG battery pack and inverter. In a typical residential installation, the electrical panel provides 120V single-phase and 240V split-phase power. The fuel cell, battery inverter, and solar PV inverter are wired directly into the panel based on their voltage compatibility. An ATS isolates the SOFC, solar PV, and battery during an outage. However, with proper electrical synchronization equipment for real-

time islanding and grid reconnection, a single ATS can be placed between the electrical panel and the utility meter. For our experimental purposes, there is virtually no difference between having the systems connected to the electrical grid through different circuits operating at different voltages and/or number of phases. This experimental setup would not be appropriate for future studies on nanogrid islanding or power quality interactions between different component inverters.

Figure 22: Mounted LG battery pack (left) and inverter (right)

4.2 ZNE Energy Technology Control Systems

Controls strategies for the dispatch of distributed energy technologies (e.g., PV, SOFC, batteries) in residences were integrated through controllers provided and managed by Heila Technologies and a smart electrical panel provided by InstantON. We purchased the hardware, software, and engineering support from these companies for installing and demonstrating novel control strategies to achieve ZNE with the integrated system. The Heila EDGE controller provided connects our systems resources which allow for the management and monitoring of our infrastructure. The controller enables the distributed energy resources to act together in well-coordinated and optimized systems. The device is used using standard Modbus communication protocols and follows the SunSpec information models. Machine learning techniques obtain the most important characteristics and optimize the performance of the system over time.

Two controllers were connected since the relocation of the ESS to another room—the controller for the devices in the previous room and a second EDGE controller to monitor and manage the ESS. Egauges, energy metering systems, and 4-20 mA current sensors are also connected to

support control functions.

Figure 23: Heila EDGE controller next to Egauge metering systems

InstantON is an energy solutions company that offers various products and services including high voltage storage, low voltage storage, mobile energy solutions, microgrid designs, and smart panels. This project looked to InstantON for their IO-HUB Smart Panel and associated guidance in the installation and control of this smart panel.

Both controllers connect to the SOFC, solar and battery inverters, and load simulators through connection ports. SOFC and battery inverter systems were configured to receive signals from the controllers specifying operational state. The Heila controller represents the optimized controller system, and the proprietary controller technology applied algorithms and optimization techniques similar to the UCI DERopt tool to determine the optimal power setting for all available energy system resources. This controller does not have predefined rules or operating schedules, instead using mathematical modeling tools to determine the lowest cost course of actions to take to ensure optimal operation. Conversely, the InstantON controller (the heuristics based controller) relies on predefined rules and schedules to govern the operation of different energy system components. For example, based on SOFC optimization analysis, two potential heuristic approaches are to 1) cycle the SOFC each day, operating the system at minimum load when solar PV is active, and operate at full load at all other hours, or 2) operate the SOFC at full load continuously. These two approaches are coded into the InstantON controller as a schedule, specifying SOFC power depending on time of day.

Figure 24: InstantON Genius smart panel near previous Energy Storage System (ESS)

4.3 Component Experimental Results

A key question addressed by our experiments is can a real SOFC and EES system perform as prescribed by our prior ZNE optimization models? Since the optimization model currently operates at an hourly time step, this means changing SOFC and EES power levels quickly enough to track the hour-to-hour energy dynamics produced by the optimization model. Because the project focuses on residential energy systems expected to operate for more than ten years, the experiments must account for both typical and extreme operating days. However, long-duration testing over months or years is impractical, so we developed representative load shapes for the controllable resources and used these to evaluate each component's ability to follow an optimal dispatch strategy.

4.3.1 Load Shape Development

The key inputs for the experimental campaign are the optimal dispatch profiles for the fuel cell and battery systems. Using the optimization data from Section 3.1, we identified specific days that were either representative of many similar days or that captured unique operational dynamics. To select these days, we applied a k-medoids clustering algorithm, which identifies representative days (medoids) that minimize the average distance to all other days in their cluster

while remaining actual members of the dataset. In our context, each medoid corresponds to a 24-hour dispatch profile, and the goal was to choose a limited set of days that both reflect the most common operating patterns and capture the full range of fuel cell dynamics indicated by the optimization. The number of clusters (and thus experimental days) was determined by increasing k until the reduction in within-cluster distance was less than 1% compared to the previous ($k-1$) case. While this stopping criterion is somewhat arbitrary, the results demonstrate that the method effectively captured both typical operating patterns and extreme dynamics for the fuel cell and battery systems.

According to this stopping criterion for selecting k days, we identified 14 unique instances of SOFC operation, as shown in Figure 25. Each medoid represents one of the 14 clusters, with the figure also indicating the number of days assigned to each cluster. Notably, 351 of the 365 days can be characterized by only three representative days. The most common mode of operation, shown in the top left of Figure 25, is the SOFC operating at full load except during solar hours; this pattern accounts for nearly 50 percent of all days. In these instances, the SOFC was operated at minimum load on peak solar days where adopted solar and storage was sufficient to meet residential loads. Conversely, maximum operation occurred when solar potential was weakest and there was insufficient solar production to continuously power the battery in the evening through the early morning.

Figure 25: K-medoid days for SOFC operation.

The next two most frequent modes involve steady-state operation at either minimum or maximum load across the entire day. The remaining clusters capture more dynamic behaviors, spread across 14 days. A common feature among these dynamic days is operation at minimum load during daylight hours followed by a sharp ramp to full power in the early evening, consistent with the California duck curve. Variations of this behavior appear in nine out of ten medoids representing dynamic operation, or 13 out of the 14 outlier days. Note that this result held constant across all climate zones, showing that SOFC operation occurred primarily in response to solar availability.

Unlike the SOFC, the k-medoid stopping criterion for battery operation was not met until k exceeded 200. This behavior is driven by two factors. First, the battery is inherently more flexible than the fuel cell, capable of faster ramping and rapid start/stop operation. Second, its

dispatch responds simultaneously to several dynamic signals, including building load, import and export electricity prices, and the TDV energy intensity signal. Together, these factors produce highly variable operation that changes on nearly a daily basis in the optimization results.

Because the clustering results for the SOFC and battery differed so significantly, we adopted two separate testing approaches. For the SOFC, we used the representative profiles shown in Figure 25. Each profile was repeated over two days, resulting in 28 total days of testing. For the battery, it was not practical to test more than 200 representative days, so the focus shifted to characterizing its dynamic response. Specifically, we examined how quickly the battery can transition from a dormant state to charging or discharging. Since battery technology is well established and residential systems are known to respond extremely quickly, the experiments emphasized determining the limits of this dynamic capability rather than verifying that the battery could follow the optimization-derived dispatch profiles.

4.3.2 SOFC Experimental Results

Results from the SOFC dynamic dispatch experiments are shown in Figure 26. The figure presents the requested power from the optimal dispatch profiles, the measured SOFC power output, and the system efficiency. Note the difference in time resolution: requested power and efficiency are shown at one-hour intervals, while SOFC power output is reported at 3-second intervals. This reflects the data sources. Requested power and efficiency come from the manufacturer's data output, which is available only on an hourly basis. In contrast, SOFC power output was measured directly using independent voltage and current measurements at the AC terminals. We selected a 3-second resolution for these measurements to capture the system's dynamic response while avoiding memory limitations that would arise with higher-frequency data collection.

Figure 26: Dynamic SOFC testing results showing the ability of the SOFC to track a dynamic load profile, and the resulting SOFC system efficiency.

The three main takeaways from these experiments are that the SOFC is capable of dynamic operation, system efficiency lags behind power output, and system efficiency suffers at part loads below 50% SOFC capacity. Figure 26 (g), for example, illustrates the most dynamic day: the fuel cell ramps from minimum power to about 1.2 kW for two hours, drops back to minimum during solar hours, and then ramps up to full power for three hours in the evening before returning to minimum for the rest of the night. During this cycle, the SOFC responds rapidly, delivering 95 to 99 percent of the requested energy over the two ramp-up events. Similar behavior is shown in, Figure 26 (i) and 26(j), where the system ramps from full load down to minimum load and then back up to full load.

The lag in fuel cell efficiency observed in Figure 26 is consistent with the expected thermal dynamics of SOFC operation. Because the system operates on natural gas, which is first partially reformed in an external unit and then fully converted within the stack, a portion of the fuel's chemical energy is consumed to sustain endothermic reforming reactions. At full load, waste

heat from the stack provides much of this energy. When the SOFC ramps down, thermal inertia in the stack and balance-of-plant continues to supply heat for methane reforming, which temporarily sustains higher efficiency at part load. As the system cools, however, more of the fuel chemical energy must be redirected to drive the reforming reactions, leading to the delayed decline in efficiency.

Further detail on SOFC part-load efficiency is provided in Figure 27, which shows system efficiency during a ramp from minimum to maximum load and then back down to minimum. These results confirm the delayed efficiency response observed in Figure 26. The data demonstrate a clear path dependence: part-load efficiency is higher when the system has ramped down from a full-load (warmer) state compared to when it has ramped up from a minimum-load (colder) state. Note that prior work has shown that SOFC performance at part load suffers in part due to balance of plant operation at part load. Motors and other systems needed to supply air and fuel are designed around single-speed motors that operate at a fixed output regardless of SOFC output.

Figure 27: SOFC system fuel to electricity conversion efficiency during dynamic dispatch experiments

One interesting feature of the optimal SOFC dispatch data is the lack of operation at part load other than at minimum load. Optimal SOFC operation oscillates between maximum and minimum production except for four hours of the year. Regardless, experimental results show that the fuel cell is capable of dynamic operation such that it can replicate the desired operation needed to achieve lowest cost operation.

4.3.3 Battery Experimental Results

Battery experimental results exceeded expectations. Figure 28 illustrates an eight-hour test in which the battery was charged and then discharged. The system's dynamic response was effectively instantaneous: it could ramp to maximum charge or discharge power faster than the data acquisition interval. Based on our measurements, the charging and discharging ramp rates exceeded 100 percent of rated power per second, meaning the battery could reach any operating point within one second. These results confirm that the battery can perform all of the dynamic operations required by the optimal dispatch for lowest-cost operation, which is consistent with the well-established fast response capabilities of modern battery systems.

Figure 28: Battery dynamics showing charging and discharging over approximately eight hours

4.4 Component Experimental Outcomes

The SOFC and battery testing demonstrate that both components can operate dynamically, enabling application of existing optimal control techniques without modification. The SOFC ramping experiments confirmed that the commercially available unit can increase and decrease power output rapidly enough to meet the generation profiles prescribed by optimization approaches.

Battery performance was even stronger. The system can transition from zero to full power—

charging or discharging—at rates faster than the resolution of our data acquisition system. This dynamic capability is critical for future research, particularly in hybrid SOFC–battery configurations. However, despite the positive SOFC results, the manufacturer advises against frequent ramping to avoid accelerated degradation. Moving from the current hourly control to a more practical real-time framework will therefore require the SOFC and battery to coordinate, with the battery clearly serving the second-to-second balancing role necessary for lowest-cost operation.

One concern identified during testing was a derating of the SOFC peak capacity. Over the course of dynamic operation experiments, the maximum output declined from 1.5 kW to 1.2 kW—a reduction of approximately 20%. The cause of this derating is uncertain, but the magnitude is significant relative to the expected gradual degradation rates typically reported for SOFCs. More troubling is that this derate was not communicated by the manufacturer. Instead, we inferred the reduction indirectly, when the system consistently failed to deliver above 1.2 kW despite commands requesting 1.4–1.5 kW.

This lack of transparency introduces two critical challenges. First, it undermines predictive control. Optimization-based controllers depend on accurate knowledge of system capabilities. When controllers assume 1.5 kW of available generation but only 1.2 kW can be delivered, the system must scramble to make up for the shortfall through grid imports, PV diversion, or battery discharge. These reactive adjustments reduce efficiency, raise costs, and compromise the value of advanced control strategies. Second, the communications failure itself forces additional layers of engineering. Instead of enabling predictive optimization, the controller must implement fallback routines to detect and triage unannounced derates—essentially designing around a black box.

From the perspective of system integration and cost minimization, this combination of silent derating and limited communication channels is as damaging as the performance loss itself. It shifts control strategies from proactive cost-optimized dispatch to reactive gap-filling, eroding both economic value and user confidence.

5 Controller Testing

We evaluate system performance with two control strategies: an optimization-based controller (Heila) that follows dispatch profiles from prior DERopt runs, and a heuristic controller (InstantON) driven by simple rules. The heuristic rules consider load profiles, utility rates, and external factors (e.g., real-time grid emission rate).

We applied k-medoids clustering to the combined SOFC–battery dispatch (over 200 clusters) and distilled consistent operating patterns into the following rules:

- **SOFC:** either (i) hold a constant setpoint at minimum or maximum load, or (ii) follow an inverse-solar profile—run at full power except when PV is producing, then drop to minimum.
- **Battery:** absorb PV excess that cannot be used onsite. In “winter” (October–May), discharge after sunset to meet residual load not served by the SOFC. In summer (June–September), prioritize discharging during peak export-price hours so unused electricity is sold back to the utility.

Based on this analysis, we tested two heuristic strategies. Combined with the optimal control strategy, a total of three strategies were tested. The two heuristic strategies are:

1. **Heuristics 1:** The fuel cell follows an inverse solar profile. The battery absorbs excess solar PV during the day. In the winter, the battery discharges in the evening to meet building load not met by the fuel cell. During the summer, the battery discharges fully when the export rate is the highest.
2. **Heuristics 2:** The fuel cell operates at full load. The battery absorbs excess solar PV during the day. In the winter, the battery discharges in the evening to meet building load not met by the fuel cell. During the summer, the battery discharges fully when the export rate is the highest.

Initial testing with the existing 5 kW solar PV and 10 kWh battery showed that this configuration is never optimal—undersized when paired with fossil natural gas and oversized when renewable

fuel is available. We therefore shifted to optimizing solar and storage capacities relative to SOFC size and scaled real system operation to match the optimized design. Control strategies were tested using a reduced-capacity 0.75 kW SOFC. Results for the 1.5 kW SOFC are excluded because this system proved uneconomic, increasing annual costs by \$200–\$4,000 compared to the 0.75 kW system. The higher costs stemmed from greater fuel input requirements or the need for larger solar and storage systems to offset fossil fuel use. Each scenario was evaluated with and without a net-zero energy constraint, under four utility gas supply assumptions: (1) fossil natural gas, (2) renewable fuel at \$2/kg H₂ equivalent, (3) renewable fuel at \$6/kg H₂, and (4) renewable fuel at \$10/kg H₂. Scenarios were also tested across three climate zones (CZ06, CZ15, and CZ16), assuming either mixed-fuel homes (gas for space heating, DHW, and appliances) or fully electrified homes using heat pumps and entry-level electric appliances.

In this analysis, ZNE scenarios either achieve net zero energy or are infeasible. Accordingly, the focus is placed on costs—specifically how ZNE requirements affect annual energy expenses. Annual cost of energy is defined as the sum of utility bills (electricity and gas), loan payments for adopted systems (SOFC, solar PV, and storage), and associated maintenance costs. For instance, achieving ZNE with solar PV and storage can nearly eliminate utility bills, but these savings are offset by debt payments that replace them. ZNE solutions that do include a SOFC focus on a 0.75 kW system. This is smaller than the 1.5 kW system used in experiments. However, our detailed analysis has shown that 1.5 kW SOFC systems are oversized and approach being uneconomic for residential applications. The primary challenge is average energy use in California falls below 1.5 kWh/hour, or 1.5 kW average power output [18]. As a result, a 1.5 kW is, on average, oversized for residential applications in California. Additionally, analysis presented in Section 3 Evaluation of SOFC Value showed that adoption a SOFC with capacities in excess of 0.9 kW rarely add value. Based on these factors, this section focuses on a 0.75 kW SOFC system.

5.1 CZ06 Results – Long Beach

For CZ06, results are benchmarked against the lowest-cost energy solution. At current solar PV, battery, and SOFC prices, the least-cost option is for a residential customer to purchase all electricity and natural gas directly from the utility. Under this case, annual utility bills are \$2,055 for mixed-fuel homes and \$1,742 for electrified homes. Both homes are net energy positive,

importing 14,844 kWh and 6,342 kWh of TDV energy, respectively. The difference reflects the higher renewable content of grid electricity and the greater efficiency of electric heating relative to gas.

When conventional natural gas is used, zero net energy (ZNE) cannot be achieved with any SOFC capacity. The fuel cell's use of conventional fuel increases the total energy that must be offset, and although this could theoretically be balanced with solar PV and storage, utility rules prohibit exporting electricity generated from systems that co-mingle renewable and fossil-derived energy. Because grid export during peak TDV periods is essential for achieving ZNE, this restriction makes it infeasible. ZNE is therefore only attainable if systems are limited to solar PV and storage. In this case, costs, installed capacities, and TDV export quantities are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary results for solar and storage systems required for a mixed-fuel and electrified home in CZ06 to achieve ZNE when operating with conventional natural gas as the fuel source

Building Scenario	Annual Cost of Energy (\$/year)	Solar Capacity (kW)	Storage Capacity (kWh)	TDV Energy Export Requirement (kWh)
Mixed-Fuel	\$5,551	4.6	37	7,002
Electrified	\$3,246	3.6	20	2,319

Results shift significantly if renewable fuel is available, since customers can export excess SOFC, solar PV, or stored electricity to the grid. With renewable fuel at \$2/kg H₂ equivalent, the optimal ZNE configuration is a 0.75 kW SOFC paired with ~1 kW solar PV, rather than larger solar-plus-storage systems. This outcome reflects the combination of relatively low renewable fuel cost, high SOFC conversion efficiency, and supplemental DHW heat recovery, making SOFC operation on renewable fuel the lowest-cost solution. Under this case, annual energy costs increase only modestly, by about 15–16%.

Replacing the optimal control strategy with either heuristic approach raises costs by \$150–\$950/year. Two factors drive this increase. First, heuristic dispatch forces adoption of larger solar and storage systems to accommodate deviations from optimal SOFC operation. For example, solar capacity rises to 3.5 kW under Heuristic 1 (reverse solar operation), while Heuristic 2 requires a small battery to absorb excess SOFC generation. Second, SOFC operation under heuristics is not dynamically coordinated with other systems needed to achieve ZNE. As shown

in Figure 29, SOFC dispatch differs markedly across the three strategies: optimal control modulates operation in real time, balancing solar and SOFC output, whereas heuristic approaches lock the system into less efficient operating patterns..

Figure 29: Differences in SOFC operation in March

Differences between the optimal control strategy and the heuristic approaches become more pronounced as renewable fuel costs increase. At \$2/kg H₂, the cost penalty for heuristics is modest—approximately \$150/year—but grows to \$450/year, or nearly 25% of baseline electricity costs, at higher fuel prices. These results demonstrate that continuous modulation of SOFC operation under optimal control remains the most cost-effective strategy. Nevertheless, even with optimal operation, higher renewable fuel prices lead to substantial increases in total energy costs, rising by 73% at \$6/kg H₂ and by 120% at \$10/kg H₂.

Regardless of fuel cost, the optimal control strategy remains the superior option from two perspectives. First, it enables cost-effective adoption of supporting technologies by avoiding unnecessary storage and allowing smaller solar PV capacities while still achieving ZNE. Excess SOFC generation above building load is dispatched either to directly meet ZNE requirements or to reduce overall cost, eliminating the need for oversized systems. Second, the optimal control strategy continuously modulates SOFC operation, preventing cost-increasing behavior that would otherwise necessitate suboptimal solar and storage adoption.

5.2 CZ15 Results – Palm Springs

CZ15 has a warmer climate than CZ06, requiring more cooling in summer and less heating in winter. Before installing onsite generation or storage, the mixed-fuel home incurs annual utility costs of \$3,404 and uses 16,806 kWh/year of TDV energy, with over 42% attributable to natural gas for heating and appliances. The electrified home is less costly and energy-intensive, with annual utility bills of \$2,103 and 7,422 kWh/year.

As in CZ06, achieving ZNE requires switching from fossil natural gas to a renewable gas blend. Because utility rules prohibit electricity export from fossil-fueled generation, SOFC systems operating on natural gas cannot achieve ZNE. Under these conditions, ZNE is possible only with solar PV and battery adoption. Optimal ZNE system designs under current natural gas and electricity conditions (Table 2) demonstrate that ZNE can be achieved, but at a significant cost premium: energy costs rise by 85% for the electrified home and by 155% for the mixed-fuel home.

Table 2: Summary results for solar and storage systems required for a mixed-fuel and electrified home in CZ15 to achieve ZNE when operating with conventional natural gas as the fuel source

Building Scenario	Annual Cost of Energy (\$/year)	Solar Capacity (kW)	Storage Capacity (kWh)	TDV Energy Export Requirement (kWh)
Mixed-Fuel	\$8,672	7.7	55	11,540
Electrified	\$3,900	4.3	22	2,948

Annual cost results for different operating strategies with renewable fuel in place of fossil natural gas are summarized in Table 3. Two main findings emerge. First, adopting an SOFC generally lowers annual energy costs, except in electrified homes when renewable fuel prices exceed \$6/kg H₂. Second, the optimal control strategy consistently reduces costs relative to either heuristic approach, with savings ranging from \$100–\$200/year at the low end to as much as \$1,000–\$2,000/year. The only exception is a \$24/year savings outlier that occurs when renewable hydrogen is priced at \$2/kg H₂, where the cost-minimizing strategy is to operate the SOFC at full output, reducing power only when demand falls below the 0.75 kW system capacity.

Table 3: Annual utility costs when achieving ZNE with access to renewable fuel for SOFC, heating, and appliance operation for CZ15

Renewable Fuel Cost (\$/kg H ₂)	Electrified			Mixed-Fuel		
	Optimal	Heuristics - 1	Heuristics - 2	Optimal	Heuristics - 1	Heuristics - 2
\$2	\$2,655	\$2,905	\$4,794	\$4,770	\$5,026	\$4,794
\$6	\$3,635	\$3,741	\$6,400	\$6,154	\$6,277	\$6,400
\$10	\$4,423	\$4,576	\$8,006	\$7,433	\$7,529	\$8,006

Results for CZ15 are more promising than CZ06. On one hand, cost of achieving ZNE increase as they do for CZ06. On the other hand, the optimal control strategy appears to be more flexible and achieve substantial reductions in cost across all renewable scenarios. Ultimately, these results show that the optimal ZNE solution includes a SOFC system as long as renewable fuel can be procured at \$6/kg H₂ or lower. If costs approach \$2/kg H₂, the cost of achieving ZNE is approximately \$500/year in increased energy cost.

5.3 CZ16 Results – Bishop

CZ16, the coldest climate zone considered, represents Bishop. Estimated annual utility costs are \$2,812 for a mixed-fuel home and \$1,950 for an electrified home, with energy use of 26,050 kWh/year and 7,431 kWh/year, respectively. Natural gas accounts for 78% of total energy use. As in CZ06 and CZ15, a SOFC cannot achieve ZNE on natural gas due to export limitations. Table 4 shows results when only solar and battery storage are used with utility-supplied natural gas. Because of high heating loads, CZ16 requires larger solar and storage systems, particularly in the mixed-fuel case. Here, reliance on natural gas for space heating, hot water, and appliances drives the largest PV and battery requirements among all climate zones studied, while raising the cost of energy by more than 400%.

Table 4: Summary results for solar and storage systems required for a mixed-fuel and electrified home in CZ16 to achieve ZNE when operating with conventional natural gas as the fuel source

Building Scenario	Annual Cost of Energy (\$/year)	Solar Capacity (kW)	Storage Capacity (kWh)	TDV Energy Export Requirement (kWh)
Mixed-Fuel	\$14,908	14.4	83	26,050
Electrified	\$3,766	4.0	23	7,431

Table 5 shows cost results for CZ16 with renewable fuel. As in CZ06 and CZ15, the optimal

control strategy yields the lowest costs, with the best heuristic approach varying by fuel price. However, CZ16 shows the smallest cost gap between optimal and heuristic strategies. Even at the highest renewable fuel prices, the difference is \$500/year or less—making CZ16 the climate zone with the lowest control strategy sensitivity among those tested.

Table 5: Annual utility costs when achieving ZNE with access to renewable fuel for SOFC, heating, and appliance operation for CZ16

Renewable Fuel Cost (\$/kg H ₂)	Electrified			Mixed-Fuel		
	Optimal	Heuristics - 1	Heuristics - 2	Optimal	Heuristics - 1	Heuristics - 2
\$2	\$2,417	\$2,686	\$2,432	\$3,501	\$3,798	\$3,512
\$6	\$3,410	\$3,521	\$3,661	\$6,178	\$6,332	\$6,339
\$10	\$4,235	\$4,357	\$4,889	\$8,764	\$8,865	\$9,166

5.4 Impact of Low Income Support Programs

All prior results considered households that do not qualify for low-income assistance. The impact of such programs depends on the type of support provided. For example, under CARE rates—where electricity is reduced by 30% and gas by 20%—outcomes are nearly identical to higher-income households, but annual energy costs fall by 20–25%. However, ZNE efforts still increase the energy burden for low-income households unless CARE subsidies are expanded.

There are also programs that subsidize up to 100% of the cost of solar and batteries for low-income households⁸. These incentives can make solar-plus-storage the lowest-cost ZNE option, but their overall impact is limited by budget caps and other constraints that restrict participation.

5.5 Summary of Results

The three key outcomes from this work are that 1) SOFC and battery systems can operate dynamically and follow load profiles suggested by optimal dispatch solutions designed to achieve lowest cost, 2) optimal control strategies produce the lowest cost operation versus heuristic approaches, and 3) optimization based controllers are able to replicate offline design optimization tool results in actual hardware.

Experimental results from the SOFC show that the system can change load settings with

⁸ Inside California, SASH-Equity and SOMAH provide funding for solar PV on low-income housing. SGIP-Equity funding provides funds for battery energy storage.

sufficient speed to match the optimal SOFC dispatch required to achieve lowest cost. The most important dynamic characteristic for the fuel cell is the speed at which the system transitions from minimum to maximum load, and then back to minimum load. The SOFC was able to respond within the hour, changing system load with sufficient speed to closely match the optimal SOFC operation load profiles developed during initial modeling and analysis. The key characteristic of the system that allows for this success is the option use a battery to buffer between the relatively slow dynamics of a SOFC versus the rapid dynamics of solar generation and residential energy demand.

Experimental efforts also showed that both the optimal and heuristic controller technologies were able to connect to different components and implement control schemes that mirrored optimal control actions to different degrees. Experimental results clearly show that the optimal controller approach outperforms the heuristic controller approach, consistently finding cost savings not available to the heuristics based controller.. The difference between optimal and heuristic control strategies is smallest when SOFC fuel is inexpensive. In this instance, optimal SOFC operation resembles full load operation captured with the 2nd heuristic control strategy. This result is nearly trivial – if electricity from the SOFC is lower cost than the electric utility or solar and storage combined, then the SOFC should be used to meet as much load as possible. If these conditions are not met and the cost of fuel increases, then the value of an optimal control strategy becomes apparent, lowering cost by hundreds to thousands of dollars per year. Regardless, experimental results show that commercially available controllers that used an optimization based approach are able to replicate modeling efforts, approaching lowest cost nanogrid operation when controlling solar PV, a battery, SOFC, and electrical utility connection.

6 Discussion

Residential SOFC systems have promise as a ZNE solution. However, the viability of this statement relies on multiple factors:

1. **Supply of renewable fuel:** SOFC systems are only viable for ZNE if powered by renewable fuel. When operated on conventional natural gas, they raise emissions and face export limitations that prevent ZNE compliance. If renewable fuel is not provided,

current electric utility rules make ZNE impossible: households cannot export electricity from fossil generation, and solar-plus-storage exports cannot consistently be verified as renewable. As a result, without renewable gas supplied by utilities, SOFC adoption increases costs and cannot meet zero-emission objectives.

2. **SOFC capacity:** Our analysis shows that the 1.5 kW SOFC system, marketed for residential use, is oversized by at least 0.75 kW. To align with household loads, SOFC systems would need to be smaller, but downsizing runs counter to typical economies of scale. Compounding this challenge, most domestic fuel cell manufacturers are pursuing larger systems, leaving few companies active in the small residential SOFC market.
3. **Combined heat and power:** CHP is critical for making SOFC systems viable in residential settings. Pairing an SOFC with domestic hot water systems enables effective use of waste heat, significantly improving overall system efficiency and cost-effectiveness.
4. **Costs of solar and battery storage:** As solar and storage costs decline, the economic benefit of adding an SOFC becomes marginal. At that point, the appeal of a straightforward solar-plus-storage system outweighs the minimal additional savings from including an SOFC, since households may prefer the simplicity and reliability of a less complex system.
5. **SOFC reliability:** SOFC performance in this study raised several concerns. We experienced unexpected outages caused by non-standard water filters failing, an unanticipated system derate, and potential long-term durability issues linked to frequent ramping. Interestingly, an earlier model of the same fuel cell operated without these problems, but the issues observed here highlight risks for residential deployment. For SOFCs to be viable in ZNE or residential applications, they must function reliably for years with minimal user intervention. A reasonable expectation is similar to a water heater or space heater: routine checkups every few years are acceptable, but frequent failures or maintenance demands would place an undue burden on ratepayers and undermine adoption.

6. **ZNE mandate:** For ZNE requirements to be mandated through the state building energy code or similar regulations, they must also demonstrate cost savings. In this work, SOFC systems did not reduce costs, due both to high capital expenses and, more importantly, the high price of renewable fuel. For SOFCs to become a viable ZNE pathway under building code mandates, electricity prices would need to rise dramatically—making alternatives more attractive—or renewable fuel costs would need to fall enough to compete with electricity on a conversion-efficiency basis. Without such shifts, SOFCs will not support cost-effective ZNE compliance, and regulatory mandates are unlikely.
7. **Equity:** Under existing low-income support programs, current ZNE requirements increase costs for households, with the impact felt most acutely by low-income ratepayers who already face high energy burdens. Conversely, programs that subsidize onsite generation overwhelmingly support solar and storage, making SOFC systems uneconomic even for ZNE applications in these households. In general, ZNE requirements without targeted equity considerations risk raising energy burdens for low-income communities, while solutions to this challenge are being advanced primarily through solar and storage rather than SOFCs.
8. **Component communication:** Effective ZNE operation with SOFCs requires a controller that can coordinate battery storage and the fuel cell based on solar generation, building load, utility rates, export rules, and grid carbon intensity. In practice, this is hampered by limited interoperability. OEMs often make it difficult to connect devices or send control signals between them. For example, it took over a year to establish communication with our battery inverter, and the ultimate solution required replacing the inverter with a different model—voiding the warranty, an unacceptable approach for real applications. While some companies offer smart home energy controls, these are generally designed as closed, whole-home solutions that exclude SOFCs. To achieve cost-effective ZNE, smart controls are essential, which in turn requires standardized communication protocols and true interoperability across residential energy systems.
9. **Optimization versus heuristics:** Our analysis showed that replicating optimal control with heuristic rules requires more than 200 conditions to account for system states, loads, and market signals. Even then, heuristics underperform compared to smart controls—

except in the rare case where fuel is so inexpensive that the optimal strategy is simply SOFC load-following. This highlights the imperative for implementing smart controls, which depend fundamentally on robust communication between all system components.

During the course of this project, the optimal controls platform provider we partnered with went out of business, underscoring the fragility of the current market for advanced residential energy controls. In practice, given existing communication and interoperability challenges, solar-plus-storage installers will continue to rely on their own integrated control platforms, which typically exclude SOFC systems. As a result, SOFCs are unlikely to emerge as a viable ZNE solution for residences unless broader market forces—such as substantially lower-cost renewable fuel and demonstrated improvements in durability—create undeniable pressure for their adoption.

Our experience with the heuristics controls provider highlights both the potential and the limitations of rules-based platforms. While these systems enable user-defined control sequences, in practice they are infeasible. With only an SOFC, battery, and solar system, we identified more than 200 unique control sequences, each dependent on shifting factors such as utility rates, equipment derates, or changing loads. Although we distilled these into two heuristic strategies, our results showed they are suboptimal and lead to higher costs. This underscores the need to rely on optimization-based controls, which can adapt to new situations and evolving market conditions in ways that fixed heuristics cannot.

7 Conclusion

This report explored the potential of SOFCs as a viable energy solution for achieving ZNE in residential buildings. The motivation for this study stems from the increasing need for cost-effective, efficient, and flexible energy technologies to meet stringent energy standards in California, particularly for electrified homes.

Key findings from the theoretical evaluation highlight the significant value that SOFCs can provide in ZNE applications. The marginal value analysis demonstrated that SOFCs offer substantial benefits by reducing the required capacity of solar PV and battery systems, thereby lowering overall system costs. However, the results also indicate that SOFC adoption is economically feasible only when hydrogen fuel costs are below \$6/kg, and system costs decrease

to match the calculated economic thresholds. Additionally, the flexibility of SOFCs to operate dynamically at partial loads further enhances their suitability for residential applications.

Physical testing of residential SOFC systems showed that these units can respond quickly to changes in load. From a controls perspective, their dynamic response is fast enough to enable lowest-cost ZNE operation, provided they can reliably ramp between minimum and maximum output. Our experiments used hourly-resolved load data, but the observed ability to transition between states demonstrates that SOFCs can meet the core operational requirements of optimization-based ZNE dispatch.

Comparison of control strategies revealed that optimization-based controls replicate lowest cost operation that match modeling analyses performed prior to system operation, and that the optimization-based controller consistently outperform heuristic approaches. While heuristics can approximate some operational modes, they require hundreds of user-defined rules and still result in higher costs. Only in the trivial case of very low renewable fuel prices—where SOFCs can run at full output with minimal adjustment—did heuristic controls approach optimal performance. In all other cases, optimal controls lowered annual costs by hundreds to thousands of dollars, underscoring their importance for practical ZNE deployment.

From an equity perspective, SOFCs do not reduce energy burden for low-income ratepayers. Existing solar and storage incentive programs already provide a low-cost ZNE pathway for these households, effectively eliminating the economic role of SOFCs. Because SOFCs require a constant fuel input, CARE discounts and similar subsidies are insufficient to offset ongoing fuel costs, meaning ZNE mandates tied to SOFCs would raise costs for low-income households.

Despite successful experiments, substantial barriers remain. Renewable fuel is essential for SOFC-based ZNE, since natural gas operation both increases emissions and runs afoul of export restrictions. System sizing is also problematic: the 1.5 kW SOFC tested is oversized for typical residential loads, and smaller systems would be needed to avoid unnecessary costs. Reliability and communication challenges are equally critical—our testing revealed unannounced derates, component outages, and persistent interoperability problems that required hardware replacements. These issues add cost and undermine the value of advanced control strategies.

Overall, this project demonstrates that while residential SOFCs can technically support ZNE, their practical viability depends on conditions that are not yet in place. Low-cost renewable fuel, smaller and more durable SOFC units, standardized communication protocols, and integration with optimization-based controls are all prerequisites. Until these factors align, solar-plus-storage will remain the dominant and most cost-effective solution for residential ZNE, while SOFC adoption will be limited to niche cases or future markets where fuel and technology costs shift decisively.

Ultimately, this research effort raised multiple questions for future research:

- Modeling results from this work show that dynamic capability is a key driver of fuel cell value in a ZNE nanogrid. Preliminary comparative analysis indicates that low-temperature proton-exchange membrane fuel cell (PEMFC) systems may offer greater operational value than the SOFCs considered here, not because of higher efficiency, but due to their superior transient performance and ability to start, stop, and modulate output rapidly. This flexibility could reduce the need for continuous minimum-load operation and enable closer real-time coordination with solar and storage resources. Future research should quantitatively evaluate PEMFC systems for stationary residential applications, including (i) technoeconomic optimization under realistic cycling and degradation models, (ii) integration with battery-driven fast-response control strategies, and (iii) experimental validation of performance under representative residential load profiles.
- Fuel cell degradation is not currently modeled in the DERopt optimization framework nor in the nanogrid controllers used in this project. During experimental testing, the SOFC system experienced an unplanned derating event that reduced maximum output, demonstrating the practical importance of incorporating degradation dynamics into both design and real-time control. Future work should integrate degradation-aware models into optimization and dispatch algorithms so that the controller can anticipate performance loss, adjust operating strategies accordingly, and ensure that any accelerated degradation is offset by corresponding reductions in total cost of energy. This includes developing predictive methods to detect and forecast degradation, updating dispatch profiles in response to declining stack capacity, and evaluating the tradeoffs between cycling-induced wear and economic performance.

- While the controllers and optimization tools can operate at real-time resolution, the house load and solar data used in this study were limited to hourly averages. A key follow-on effort is a field demonstration that collects and uses 1-second building load and solar data to evaluate coordinated SOFC or PEMFC operation with battery storage under realistic dynamic conditions. This would allow testing how the fuel cell responds to slower multi-minute demand trends while the battery manages second-scale fluctuations, providing a more accurate assessment of performance, degradation behavior, and total cost of energy in residential operation.
- Solar PV and battery systems are commonly installed together using well-established communication standards and inverter interoperability practices, but fuel cell systems are typically delivered as standalone generators with proprietary control and monitoring interfaces. As a result, system integrators currently bear the full burden of coordinating dispatch, safety logic, metering, and controller communication across components from different vendors. A key follow-on research direction is to develop and validate standardized communications, control handoffs, and plug-and-play integration practices that enable SOFC or PEMFC systems to be installed alongside solar and storage using the same controller and commissioning workflow. This work should include collaboration with fuel cell OEMs, inverter manufacturers, and controller developers to support seamless interoperability in residential nanogrids.
- Modeling results indicate that optimal fuel cell capacity for residential ZNE operation depends strongly on dynamic capability. For SOFC systems, limited ramping and continuous minimum-load requirements mean that sub-kilowatt ($\approx 0.3\text{--}0.9$ kW) units are the most cost-effective, avoiding extended part-load operation. In contrast, PEMFC systems can operate effectively at larger capacities (up to ~ 2 kW) due to their ability to start, stop, and modulate rapidly without requiring sustained baseline operation. A key follow-on research effort is to design and evaluate modular SOFC and PEMFC system architectures sized to align with these operational characteristics, and to test their performance in coordinated operation with batteries under realistic residential load profiles.

8 References

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Appendix A: DERopt Model

The DERopt techno-economic optimization model is formulated as a mixed integer linear program. This type of problem includes a combination of integer, binary, and continuous decisions. In general, integer decisions are associated with the adoption of discrete energy systems (i.e., a fuel cell), binary decisions are associated with achieving equipment operational state and/or specific operational requirements (i.e., achieving a sufficiently low fuel cell electricity carbon intensity to enable export), and continuous decisions are associated with energy flows. The general form of optimization problem is in the following form [19]:

$$\text{minimize } f(\mathbf{S}, \mathbf{e}) \quad (6)$$

$f(\mathbf{S}, \mathbf{e})$: objective function

Subject to:

$$\mathbf{S}^{\min} \leq \mathbf{S} < \mathbf{S}^{\max} \quad \mathbf{S}: \text{ set of design variables (type/size of each component)}$$

$$\mathbf{e}^{\min} \leq \mathbf{e} < \mathbf{e}^{\max} \quad \mathbf{e}: \text{ set of control variables (dispatch variables of each component)}$$

$$\mathbf{g}_i(\mathbf{S}, \mathbf{e}) \leq \mathbf{0} \quad : \text{ inequality constraints}$$

$$\mathbf{h}_i(\mathbf{S}, \mathbf{e}) = \mathbf{0} \quad : \text{ equality constraints}$$

In the current work, the objective function, $f(\mathbf{S}, \mathbf{e})$, is a cost function that minimizes the total annual cost of energy. DER technologies includes solar PV, SOFC, and battery systems. The model also includes utility gas and electricity connections. The model also allows from the building back to the grid to increase savings and/or achieve ZNE. This section described the DERopt model in detail.

8.1 Introduction of sets, decision variables, and parameters used in DERopt

The following set t is used in the cost function model:

- $t \in T$: Set of all hourly increments in a year

Table 6. List of parameters used in DERopt model

Building	Description	Unit
$d_{el-bldg,t}$	Building electric energy demand during time t	kWh
$d_{th-bldg,t}$	Building thermal energy demand during time t	kWh
$d_{hw-bldg,t}$	Building hot water energy demand during time t	kWh
Utility Cost Parameters		
$C_{el-imp,t}$	Cost of utility electricity imported at time t	\$/kWh
$C_{el-exp,t}$	Cost of electricity exported to the grid at time t	\$/kWh
$C_{g-imp,t}$	Cost of utility gas imported at time t	\$/kWh
$C_{CO_2,t}$	Carbon emission cost of utility electricity at time t	\$/therm
DER	Description	Unit
Solar Photovoltaic (PV)		
C_{PV}^{cap}	Capital cost of solar PV system	\$/kW
$C_{PV}^{O\&M}$	O&M cost of solar PV system (0.001)	\$/kWh
η_{PV}	Conversion efficiency of each kW/m ² of solar radiation to electricity under the standard test conditions (20)	% of kW/m ²
$e_{insol,t}$	Solar insolation during t	kWh/m ²
A_{max-PV}	Max area available for PV installation (200)	m ²
Electric Energy Storage (EES) and Renewable EES (REES)		
$C_{EES}^{cap}, C_{REES}^{cap}$	Capital cost of EES, REES	\$/kWh
$C_{EES,ch}^{O\&M}, C_{REES,ch}^{O\&M}$	O&M cost to charge EES, REES (0.001)	\$/kWh
$C_{EES,dch}^{O\&M}, C_{REES,dch}^{O\&M}$	O&M cost to discharge EES, REES (0.001)	\$/kWh
$\bar{\delta}_{EES}, \bar{\delta}_{REES}$	Maximum EES/REES state of charge (95)	% Capacity
$\underline{\delta}_{EES}, \underline{\delta}_{REES}$	Minimum EES/ REES state of charge (10)	% Capacity

$\bar{\mu}_{EES}, \bar{\mu}_{REES}$	Maximum EES/ REES charging rate (50)	% Capacity
$\underline{\mu}_{EES}, \underline{\mu}_{REES}$	Maximum EES/ REES discharging rate (50)	% Capacity
$\eta_{EES_{ch}}, \eta_{REES_{ch}}$	EES/REES charging efficiency (90)	%
$\eta_{EES_{dch}}, \eta_{REES_{dch}}$	EES/REES discharging efficiency (90)	%
$\alpha_{EES}, \alpha_{REES}$	Self-discharge rate of EES/REES (99.99)	%
Solid Oxide Fuel Cell (SOFC)		
C_{SOFC}^{cap}	Capital cost of SOFC system	\$/kW _e
$C_{SOFC}^{O\&M}$	O&M cost of SOFC system (6 % of C_{SOFC}^{cap})	\$/kWh _e
η_{e-SOFC}	SOFC electric efficiency (60)	%
$\eta_{hw-SOFC}$	SOFC heat/hot water generation efficiency (30)	%
S_{SOFC}	Size of a unit SOFC system (0.5)	kW
P_{SOFC}^{min}	SOFC minimum load setting (50% of rated power)	kW
$R_{rmp-SOFC}$	SOFC ramping up /down rate (6)	%
Thermal Energy Storage (TES)		
$\bar{\delta}_{TES}$	Maximum TES tank state of charge (80 gallon / 20 kWh)	20 kWh
$\eta_{TES_{ch}}$	TES charging efficiency (95)	%
$\eta_{TES_{dch}}$	TES discharging efficiency (95)	%
α_{TES}	Self-discharge rate of TES (99.99)	%
Building space heating and hot water equipment		
η_{GSH}	Gas space heater efficiency	%
η_{GWH}	Gas water heater efficiency	%
η_{ESH}	Electric space heater efficiency	%
η_{EWH}	Electric water heater efficiency	%
Conversion factor (power to energy)		

Δt	Hourly time step (1)	hour
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Variable	Description	Type & Number
Electricity and Gas Utility Variables		
$e_{gr-imp,t}$	Electricity imported from the grid at time t (kWh)	Continuous 8760
$e_{gr-exp,t}$	Electricity exported to the grid at time t (kWh)	Continuous 8760
$g_{gr-imp,t}$	Gas imported from the grid at time t (kWh)	Continuous 8760
Solar Photovoltaic (PV)		
S_{PV}	PV system size purchased (kW)	Continuous 1
$e_{el-PV,t}$	PV electricity directly used for building during t (kWh)	Continuous 8760
$e_{st-PV,t}$	PV electricity stored in the battery during t (kWh)	Continuous 8760
$e_{exp-PV,t}$	PV electricity exported to the grid during t (kWh)	Continuous 8760
Battery (EES)		
S_{EES}	EES capacity adopted (kWh)	Continuous 1
$e_{ch-EES,t}$	Electricity charged by EES during t (kWh)	Continuous 8760
$e_{dch-EES,t}$	EES electricity discharged to building during t (kWh)	Continuous 8760

$e_{EES,t}$	EES state of charge during t (kWh)	Continuous 8760
Battery (REES)		
S_{REES}	REES capacity adopted (kWh)	Continuous 1
$e_{ch-REES,t}$	Electricity charged by REES during t (kWh)	Continuous 8760
$e_{dch-REES,t}$	REES electricity discharged to building during t (kWh)	Continuous 8760
$e_{exp-REES,t}$	REES electricity exported to the grid during t (kWh)	Continuous 8760
$e_{REES,t}$	REES state of charge during t (kWh)	Continuous 8760
Solid Oxide Fuel Cell (SOFC)		
N_{SOFC}	Number of installed SOFC systems with 0.5 kW capacity	Integer 1
$e_{SOFC,t}$	SOFC electricity output during t (kWh)	Continuous 8760
$hw_{SOFC,t}$	Hot water directly used for building during t (kWh)	Continuous 8760
Thermal Energy Storage (TES)		
$hw_{dch-TES,t}$	Hot water discharged from TES tank during t	Continuous 8760
$hw_{ch-TES,t}$	SOFC cogenerated hot water stored in TES during t	Continuous 8760

$hw_{TES,t}$	TES state of charge during t	Continuous 8760
Building space heating and hot water heater equipment		
S_{GSH}	Gas space heater (GSH) capacity (kW)	Continuous 1
$g_{GSH,t}$	Gas consumption by GSH during t (kWh)	Continuous 8760
S_{GWH}	Gas water heater (GWH) capacity (kW)	Continuous 1
$g_{GWH,t}$	Gas consumption by GWH during t (kWh)	Continuous 8760
S_{ESH}	Electric space heater (ESH) capacity (kW)	Continuous 1
$e_{ESH,t}$	Electricity consumption by ESH during t (kWh)	Continuous 8760
S_{EWH}	Electric water heater (EWH) capacity (kW)	Continuous 1
$e_{EWH,t}$	Electricity consumption by EWH during t (kWh)	Continuous 8760

For electric space and water heaters, different technologies are considered: electric resistive heaters with efficiencies equal or less than 100%; and heat pumps with coefficient of performance greater than 1. In this work, we show both types of electric heaters versus gas heaters, while the efficiency values vary depending on the technology type. Details of these heating technologies are provided in Section 2.1.

8.2 Cost Function

The objective function (shown in Equation (6)) is the total annualized cost of building energy. This includes utility bills, equipment capital, and equipment O&M. Fixed costs depend on the capacity of different energy supply and storage units that are purchased for the building. The size of each component (SOFC, PV, EES, and REES - shown as S_i) and the output energy from each component or utility source at each time step (shown as e_i) is a decision variable of the problem.

$$\begin{aligned}
 f(S, e) = & \left(S_{PV} C_{PV}^{cap} + \sum_1^{8760} (e_{el-PV,t} + e_{st-PV,t} + e_{exp-PV,t}) C_{PV}^{O\&M} \right) \\
 & + \left(S_{EES} C_{EES}^{cap} + \sum_1^{8760} (e_{dch-EES,t} + e_{ch-EES,t}) C_{EES}^{O\&M} \right) \\
 & + \left(S_{REES} C_{REES}^{cap} + \sum_1^{8760} (e_{dch-REES,t} + e_{exp-REES,t} + e_{ch-REES,t}) C_{REES}^{O\&M} \right) \\
 & + \left(S_{SOFC} C_{SOFC}^{cap} + \sum_1^{8760} e_{SOFC,t} C_{SOFC}^{O\&M} + \sum_1^{8760} \frac{e_{SOFC,t}}{\eta_{el-SOFC}} C_{g-imp,t} \right) \\
 & + \left(\sum_1^{8760} g_{gr-imp,t} C_{g-imp,t} \right) + \left(\sum_1^{8760} e_{gr-imp,t} C_{el-imp,t} \right) \\
 & - \left(\sum_1^{8760} e_{gr-exp,t} C_{el-exp,t} \right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

The total gas imported from the grid during time step t is shown in Equation (8).

$$g_{gr-imp,t} = \frac{e_{SOFC,t}}{\eta_{el-SOFC}} C_{g-imp,t} + g_{GWH,t} + g_{GSH,t} \tag{8}$$

All decision variables must be equal to or greater than zero (lower bound). Equality and inequality constraints are set to ensure the following:

- All building energy demands (electricity, heating, and hot water) are met at any given time
- At the end of the year, the total time dependent value of imported energy is less than or equal to the total time dependent value of exported energy
- The energy output from each DER equipment is limited by its installed capacity
- Since battery is allowed to only export renewable electricity to the grid, REES is constrained to be charged only by PV; also, it is the only battery that discharges electricity to the grid and building. EES electricity is only discharged to the building.
- The charging/discharging energy of all batteries are limited to their capacities and the maximum charge/discharge rates; also, their state of charges is limited to the allowable minimum and maximum levels
- Ramp up and ramp down rate of SOFC are limited to reduce the wear and tear from thermal cycle and mechanical stress. In this the ramping rate is limited to 0.5 W/s (1.8 kW/h) to avoid rapid SOFC dynamics [20].

The minimum partial load of SOFC is assumed to be 50% of its maximum capacity to avoid its complete cool down and start-up costs. The complete list of constraints is provided in Table 7.

Table 7. Equality and inequality constraints to be satisfied by the optimal solution from DERopt

General constraints (equalities)	
Description	Formula
Electricity demand	$d_{el-bldg,t} + e_{ch-EES,t} + e_{EWH,t} + e_{ESH,t}$ $= e_{el-PV,t} + e_{el-SOFC,t} + e_{dch-EES,t} + e_{dch-REES,t}$ $+ e_{gr-imp,t}$
Space heating demand	$d_{th-bldg,t} = g_{GSH,t} \eta_{GSH} + e_{ESH,t} \eta_{ESH}$

Domestic hot water demand	$d_{hw-bldg,t} = g_{GWH,t} \eta_{GWH} + e_{ERH,t} \eta_{ERH} + hw_{SOFC,t} + hw_{dch-TEs,t}$
Grid and utility interactions constraints (inequalities)	
Electricity export income does not exceed the electricity import cost	$(e_{exp-PV,t} + e_{exp-REES,t}) C_{el-exp,t} \leq e_{gr-imp,t} C_{el-imp,t}$
Total electricity export does not exceed the electricity import	$\sum_1^{8760} (e_{exp-PV,t} + e_{exp-REES,t}) \leq \sum_1^{8760} e_{gr-imp,t}$
Zero net energy (ZNE) constraint based on time dependent value (TDV) of primary energy	$\sum_1^{8760} e_{gr-imp,t} TDV_{el_imp,t} + \sum_1^{8760} g_{gr-imp,t} TDV_{g_imp,t} \leq \sum_1^{8760} e_{exp-PV,t} TDV_{el_exp,t} + \sum_1^{8760} e_{exp-REES,t} TDV_{el_exp,t}$
PV constraints (inequalities)	
Installed PV capacity is limited by maximum area	$S_{PV} \leq \eta_{PV} A_{max-PV}$
PV output is limited by the installed capacity (t = 1 hr)	$e_{el-PV,t} + e_{st-PV,t} + e_{exp-PV,t} \leq S_{PV} t$
PV production is limited by the available solar insolation at a given time	$e_{el-PV,t} + e_{st-PV,t} + e_{exp-PV,t} \leq e_{insol,t} \frac{S_{PV}}{\eta_{PV}}$
Battery (EES) constraints	
Same initial & final SOC	$e_{EES,0} \leq e_{EES,8760}$
EES energy balance	$e_{EES,t} = e_{EES,(t-1)} \alpha_{EES} + \eta_{EES_{ch}} e_{ch-EES,t} - \frac{e_{dch-EES,t}}{\eta_{EES_{dch}}}$
Limit EES state of charge to its installed capacity	$\underline{\delta}_{EES} S_{EES} \leq e_{EES,t} \leq \bar{\delta}_{EES} S_{EES}$
Limit EES charging rate	$0 \leq e_{ch-EES,t} \leq \bar{\mu}_{EES} S_{EES}$
Limit EES discharging rate	$0 \leq e_{dch-EES,t} \leq \underline{\mu}_{EES} S_{EES}$

Battery (REES) constraints	
Initial REES electricity exported to the grid	$e_{\text{exp-REES},0} = 0$
REES energy balance	$e_{\text{REES},t} = e_{\text{REES},(t-1)} \alpha_{\text{REES}} + \eta_{\text{REESch}} e_{\text{ch-REES},t} - \frac{(e_{\text{dch-REES},t} + e_{\text{exp-REES},t})}{\eta_{\text{REESdch}}}$
Limit REES state of charge to its installed capacity	$\underline{\delta}_{\text{REES}} S_{\text{REES}} \leq e_{\text{REES},t} \leq \bar{\delta}_{\text{REES}} S_{\text{REES}}$
Limit REES charging rate	$0 \leq e_{\text{ch-REES},t} \leq \bar{\mu}_{\text{REES}} S_{\text{REES}}$
Limit REES discharging rate	$0 \leq (e_{\text{dch-REES},t} + e_{\text{exp-REES},t}) \leq \underline{\mu}_{\text{REES}} S_{\text{REES}}$
SOFC constraints	
Electricity generated by SOFC is limited by the number and size of SOFCs and their minimum load	$N_{\text{SOFC}} S_{\text{SOFC}} P_{\text{SOFC}}^{\text{min}} \leq e_{\text{SOFC},t} \leq N_{\text{SOFC}} S_{\text{SOFC}}$
Hot water recovery from SOFC is limited to electricity output and efficiency	$hw_{\text{SOFC},t} + hw_{\text{ch-TEs},t} \leq \frac{e_{\text{SOFC},t}}{\eta_{\text{e-SOFC}}} \eta_{\text{hw-SOFC}}$
Limit SOFC ramp-up rate	$e_{\text{SOFC},t} - e_{\text{SOFC},(t-1)} \leq R_{\text{rmp-SOFC}} S_{\text{SOFC}} N_{\text{SOFC}}$
Limit SOFC ramp-down rate	$-R_{\text{rmp-SOFC}} S_{\text{SOFC}} N_{\text{SOFC}} \leq e_{\text{SOFC},t} - e_{\text{SOFC},(t-1)}$
TES constraints	
Same initial & final SOC	$hw_{\text{TES},0} = hw_{\text{TES},8760}$
TES tank hot water balance	$hw_{\text{TES},t} = hw_{\text{TES},(t-1)} \alpha_{\text{TES}} + \eta_{\text{TESch}} hw_{\text{ch-TEs},t} - \frac{hw_{\text{dch-TEs},t}}{\eta_{\text{TESdch}}}$
Limit the hot water level	$0 \leq hw_{\text{TES},t} \leq \bar{\delta}_{\text{TES}}$
Building space heating and hot water heater equipment	
Heating output from GSH is limited by installed capacity	$g_{\text{GSH},t} \leq \frac{S_{\text{GSH}} \Delta t}{\eta_{\text{GSH}}}$

Hot water from GWH is limited by installed capacity	$g_{GWH,t} \leq \frac{S_{GWH} \Delta t}{\eta_{GWH}}$
Heating output from ERSH is limited by installed capacity	$e_{ESH,t} \leq \frac{S_{ESH} \Delta t}{\eta_{ESH}}$
Hot water from ERWH is limited by installed capacity	$e_{EWH,t} \leq \frac{S_{EWH} \Delta t}{\eta_{EWH}}$

The objective function, decision variables, and constraints are developed in MATLAB R2014b [21] where toolboxes such as CPLEX Optimization Studio V12.8.0 [22] and YALMIP [23,24] are used for an efficient and rapid solving of the linear mixed integer optimization problem.

8.3 Summary of model input and assumptions

The input data for techno-economic analysis, optimized design, and operation of a nanogrid residential system in CZ06 is presented in

Table 8. The table includes the cost assumptions for 3 years: 2025, 2035, and 2045; the utility retail rates are assumed to be the values in each mid-decade. It is worth noting that the HP performance depends on the weather; the table shows the data for CZ06 where the water HP coefficient of performance (shown as η_{EWH}) is 2.46. While all the cost assumptions for CZ16 and CZ15 are similar, η_{EWH} of water HP in CZ16 and CZ15 are 1.65 and 2.65, respectively.

Table 8. Summary of input data and assumptions in DERopt model

Climate Zone	CZ6: LAX-UCI		(2025-2035)	(2035-2045)	(2045-2055)
Technology cost	PV (O&M=0.001(\$/kWh _e))		\$2484	\$1944	\$1317.5
	Battery (O&M=0.001(\$/kWh _e))		\$911.5	\$755	\$654
	SOFC (O&M=0.06 (\$/kWh _e))		\$5706	\$5529.5	\$5420.5
Retail rates For mid-decade	Import: RPS (%) cost adder (\$/kWh)		30% \$0.015/kWh	60% \$0.031 /kWh	100% \$0.054/kWh
	Export		NEM 2.0	NEM 3.0 (AC)	NEM 3.0 (AC)
	H ₂ fraction (by volume)		51%	86%	100%
	H ₂ cost		\$6/kg	\$4.5/kg	\$4/kg
	Cost of carbon		\$27.96/ton	\$50/ton	\$71.5/ton
Incentives	PV		MACRS:5 ITC: 1	MACRS: 0 ITC: 0	MACRS: 0 ITC: 0
	EES		MACRS:7 ITC: 0	MACRS: 0 ITC: 0	MACRS: 0 ITC: 0
	REES		MACRS:5 ITC: 1	MACRS: 0 ITC: 0	MACRS: 0 ITC: 0
	SOFC		TC: 30 %	TC: 30 %	TC: 30 %
Building Scenarios	1- Baseline (Appliance: gas)	Water Heater (η _{GWH})	Tank Gas (0.6)	Tank Gas (0.6)	Tank Gas (0.6)
		Space Heater (η _{GSH})	Gas (0.8)	Gas (0.8)	Gas (0.8)
	2- Premium Gas (Appliance: gas)	Water Heater (η _{GWH})	Condensing On-Demand Gas (0.96)	Condensing On-Demand Gas (0.96)	Condensing On-Demand Gas (0.96)
		Space Heater (η _{GSH})	Condensing Gas (0.96)	Condensing Gas (0.96)	Condensing Gas (0.96)
	3- Electric Resistive (Appliance: Electric)	Water Heater (η _{EWH})	Tank (0.9)	----	----
		Space Heater (η _{ESH})	Central Furnace (1.0)	----	----
	4- Premium Electric Resistive (Appliance: Electric)	Water Heater (η _{EWH})	On-Demand (η _{EWH})	----	----
		Space Heater (η _{ESH})	Central Furnace (1.0)	----	----
	5- Heat Pump (Appliance: Electric)	Water Heater (η _{EWH})	Hot Water HP (2.6)	Hot Water HP (2.6)	Hot Water HP (2.6)
		Space Heater (AFUE or SEER/HSPF)	Air-Source Heat Pump (14 / 8.2)	Air-Source Heat Pump (14 / 8.2)	Air-Source Heat Pump (14 / 8.2)
	6- Premium Heat Pump (Appliance: Electric)	Water Heater (η _{EWH})	Hot Water HP (2.6)	Hot Water HP (2.6)	Hot Water HP (2.6)
		Space Heater (AFUE or SEER/HSPF)	Mini-Split Ductless (29.3/14)	Mini-Split Ductless (29.3/14)	Mini-Split Ductless (29.3/14)